

Preparation of the Country Packages in Gabon (CP-Gabon)

Scientific and capacity-building component

Strategy and action plan

Libreville, 22-24 November 2023

Ministry of Water and Forests, Environmental Preservation, Climate and Human-Wildlife Conflict

Financial support

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1 Country Packages

1.1 General context

The Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework aims to protect at least 30% of land and 30% of sea by 2030. However, existing market mechanisms and the current price of carbon credits are insufficient to support large-scale conservation. Country Packages (CP) are proposed as integrated solutions to ensure sustainable financing for the conservation of these crucial areas. CPs offer technical, scientific, financial and diplomatic support and commercial partnerships to countries committed to protecting their lands and seas. The aim is to mobilise new and additional international funding sources from public, private, multilateral and philanthropic institutions to achieve these ambitious conservation goals.

1.2 Background and agenda

At COP27, France, in collaboration with Colombia, the Philippines, and Gabon, proposed creating new financial and political contracts to encourage governments to protect the world's vital carbon and biodiversity reserves. In partnership with the United States, Costa Rica, China, the Global Environment Facility (GEF) and the World Bank, France has launched Positive Conservation Partnerships (PCP). At the same time, the Forest and Climate Leaders Partnership (FCLP) was set up to maintain political leadership on forest and climate issues, focusing on Forest and Land Use Investment Packs (FLIPs) in key forest countries.

The One Forest Summit (OFS), jointly organised by France and Gabon in Libreville in March 2023, provided an opportunity for governments to take forward the CFP initiative and for scientists to discuss the scientific and technical support needed for their implementation through workshops and conferences. A consortium of French research institutions also presented a One Forest Vision (OFV) scientific initiative at the summit.

At the G7 summit in Hiroshima in May 2023, leaders expressed their support for FLIPs by referring to "Country Packages" for countries with vital carbon and biodiversity reserves. These CP constitute the new integrated implementation framework for the PCP, FCLP and FLIP, which was discussed at the Summit for a New Global Financial Deal in Paris in June 2023.

The aim is to conclude equitable agreements with the first interested countries by the time of the Amazon Summit (August 2023), the Three Basins Summit (October 2023) and COP28 (December 2023) to significantly increase both the area and the quality of conservation of forest and marine ecosystems.

1.3 CP development process in target countries

CP development model is based on the following action stages:

1.3.1 Stage 1 - Identification of priority areas

- Identifying priority areas is based on the needs expressed by the partner country.

- Sound scientific and financial analyses are carried out to assess conservation needs.
- Mapping ongoing or planned activities in these areas is carried out to avoid conflicts of interest.
- These countries ' civil society and economic players are consulted to consider their perspectives.
- In-depth studies or consultations may be necessary to clarify the needs or funding required.
- Seed funding or technical assistance may be provided to facilitate this stage.

1.3.2 *Stage 2 - Launch*

- The CP is formalised by an agreement between the partner country and public and private donors and philanthropic organisations willing to provide technical and financial support for implementing the programme.
- The country is implementing an ambitious programme of action to achieve the 30x30 land and sea protection targets, including preserving crucial carbon and biodiversity reserves and the ecological transition of its land use model.
- The partnerships include scientific support and capacity-building programmes to help the country achieve its conservation and ecological transition objectives.

In short, the CP is based on a collaborative approach between the partner country and the donors, involving in-depth consultations, rigorous analyses and support programmes to ensure the successful implementation of ambitious conservation and ecological transition measures.

1.3.3 *Financing scheme*

The funding scheme for a CP is designed to ensure the sustainability of the country's conservation policies by combining actions at national and international levels. The CP takes the form of a political declaration comprising the following elements:

1.3.3.1 *Commitments by the beneficiary country*

The CP beneficiary country defines its ambition by adhering to 30x30 protection of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework and committing to fight deforestation following the guidelines of the Paris Agreement.

Concrete objectives are established, such as identifying priority reserves to be protected, specific activities to be undertaken, a defined timetable and a clear commitment by the country to align its policies and national biodiversity financing plan.

The overall objective is to put in place a solid framework to ensure the effective implementation of conservation actions, focusing on protecting ecosystems and biodiversity while contributing to the fight against climate change through relevant international agreements.

1.3.3.2 *Financial commitment from international partners*

International partners commit to providing specified funding to support the objectives of the CP. A detailed funding plan is developed, including modalities for the disbursement of funds and a rigorous monitoring and evaluation system to ensure transparency and accountability.

Sources of funding include:

- Traditional loans and grants from international donors (bilateral and multilateral).
- Strategic mobilisation of private capital and businesses to support climate and biodiversity objectives, using risk mitigation instruments and investments in supply chains, for example.
- Use innovative financing mechanisms such as green bonds, debt swaps and performance-based payments (PFPs).
- The introduction of innovative credits makes it possible to put a value on protecting biodiversity and ecosystems.

By combining different sources of national and international funding, the CP aims to provide adequate support for implementing the country's conservation policies and achieve ambitious goals in protecting biodiversity and combating climate change. In this way, the partnership promotes a comprehensive and coordinated approach to environmental protection.

1.3.4 Scientific and capacity development process

The CP require strong scientific, technical and capacity development support to succeed. This support must be collaborative with the scientific and technical community in the country concerned and supported by international players, NGOs, and companies with relevant operational data and methods.

The scientific position must be broad and interdisciplinary, covering the interactions between climate, forests and carbon, biodiversity inventories, wetland expansion, deforestation prevention, and territorial planning. It must also include the co-construction of sustainable solutions with local stakeholders, access to and sovereignty over scientific data, and the financial valuation of conservation efforts through carbon and biodiversity certificates.

A programme to develop national research capacities and infrastructures is essential to guarantee data sovereignty and train new generations of conservation experts.

In short, CPs need robust scientific support, an interdisciplinary approach and capacity building to ensure sustainable conservation and achieve their ambitious objectives.

2 Setting up the CP-Gabon: links with the regional scientific initiatives *One Forest Vision* and *Congo Basin Science Initiative/Science Panel for the Congo Basin*

2.1 Gabon-France talks to set up the CP-Gabon

2.1.1 Context

Despite its position as the planet's first green lung, the Congo Basin, comprising the sizeable hydrographic system of the Congolese basin and the watersheds of the Atlantic coast, including that of the Ogooué in Gabon (84% of the country's surface area), remains

largely unknown and under-inventoried. Gabon's forests, covering 88% of the country, are part of this complex. Every year, they absorb 100 million tonnes of CO₂, a third of France's emissions. Gabon is firmly committed to protecting these forests at international and national levels and is a signatory to the Paris Agreement and the Kunming-Montreal Global Framework for Biodiversity.

However, Gabon, like other Central African countries, faces limited knowledge of crucial environmental services such as carbon sequestration and temperature and precipitation regulation at global, continental and regional scales. The significant constraints on research include the extent of the forests, difficult access, the limited resources of local institutions and the lack of global scientific investment. As a result, the volume of research is insufficient, and there is a lack of research and innovation structures and reliable long-term data for modelling the evolution of socio-ecosystems in the region.

2.1.2 Mission of the French Ambassador for the Environment

On a mission to Libreville from 23 to 26 July 2023, a delegation led by the French Ambassador for the Environment, Sylvie Lemmet, met with Gabonese representatives to discuss four main issues to continue negotiations to set up a CP in Gabon coordinated by France and Norway:

1. Conservation and achieving the 30x30,
2. The sustainable timber industry,
3. Financing via carbon credits,
4. Scientific support.

The visit concluded with a meeting with Professor Lee White, Gabon's former Minister for Water, Forests, the Sea and the Environment. In addition to the four initial areas of focus identified, other relevant topics emerged that could be considered for implementing the CP-Gabon. The main themes discussed included:

1. Biodiversity conservation,
2. The promotion of sustainable value chains in the forestry industry,
3. The development of income-generating activities for local communities,
4. The management of human-wildlife conflicts, with particular emphasis on interactions with elephants,
5. Raising awareness of environmental education,
6. Exploring innovative financing mechanisms, such as carbon credits,
7. Enhancing scientific knowledge,
8. Improving skills and institutional reforms.

This diversity of topics reflects the holistic and multidimensional scope of the CP-Gabon. These discussions provide a solid basis for developing a global strategy to promote environmental sustainability and support local communities in preserving Gabon's natural resources.

A schedule of meetings between Gabon and France leading up to COP28 has been drawn up to continue discussions on the main lines of action for implementing the CP-Gabon with all the technical and financial partners likely to contribute.

2.1.3 Scientific and capacity-building component

During the Ambassador for the Environment's mission, a good opportunity arose to assess the progress of the OFV initiative, which is showing promising advances in the Congo Basin and, in particular, in Gabon. The OFV is a tool for promoting collaborative research in support of the CP-Gabon approach.

The initial aim is to increase the country's capacity to monitor forest degradation, carbon reserves and biological diversity. The part of the OFV initiative dedicated to Gabon is the subject of a consultation with CENAREST.

Various areas of research are needed to achieve the objectives of the CP-Gabon. These include identifying sites to be included in the "30x30" initiative, monitoring biodiversity inside and outside protected areas, and evaluating carbon reserves with a view to offsetting. To meet these challenges, the OFV is structured around five pillars:

- Field understanding of forest carbon and biodiversity at landscape scale.
- Planning: large-scale carbon assessment of tropical forests.
- Use of remote sensing and artificial intelligence down to tree scale.
- Developing and integrating advanced mapping and monitoring products into national, regional and international systems.
- Strengthening the skills, training and involvement of citizen science.

2.2 The regional scientific initiative launched by the environment ministers of the Gabon, CAR, DRC, Congo and Cameroon sub-regions

Given the gaps in our knowledge of the ecosystems of the Congo Basin, Professor Lee White, the former Minister for Water, Forests, the Sea and the Environment of Gabon, in collaboration with the Environment Ministers of the other countries in the sub-region (CAR, DRC, Congo and Cameroon), and a group of scientists working in the region, have launched an appeal for a significant investment in science and scientists in the Congo Basin¹.

The successful Large-Scale Biosphere-Atmosphere Experiment inspired them in Amazonia (LBA), which required over \$200 million in funding over a decade. The LBA's 120 coordinated projects have profoundly transformed Brazilian tropical forest science and our understanding of the Amazon by investing in new measurements and training hundreds of Brazilian scientists.

Following this example, the appeal by the ministers and scientists of the Congo Basin aims to mobilise similar resources to improve research and understanding of the region's ecosystems. Such investment could significantly improve our understanding of the biodiversity, carbon sequestration and essential environmental services these vital forests provide. Training more local scientists and developing coordinated research projects

¹ White, L. J., Masudi, E. B., Ndongo, J. D., Matondo, R., Ngomanda, A., Averti, I. S., Ewango, C. E., Sonké, B., & Lewis, S. L. (2021). Congo Basin rainforest — Invest US\$150 million in science. *Nature*, 598(7881), 411-414. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-021-02818-7>

would also help to strengthen the region's scientific capacity and promote initiatives for the conservation and sustainable management of natural resources.

As a follow-up to this plea and in the run-up to the One Forest Summit at the end of February 2023, scientists from the Congo Basin region met with the architects of the LBA in Libreville, Gabon. The 49 scientists attending the workshop agreed to create two key initiatives to strengthen the role of science and scientists in the Congo Basin. The United Nations Sustainable Development Solutions Networks support these two initiatives. They are:

- **The Congo Basin Science Initiative (CBSI)²** aims to stimulate investment in understanding how the Congo Basin works and training a new generation of scientists. The aim is to provide the capacity to deliver the innovative policies that Congo Basin countries need to meet their commitments on climate (e.g. the INDCs) and biodiversity (e.g. the 30x30s), [<https://congobasinscience.net/fr/>].
- **The Scientific Panel for The Congo Basin (SPCB)** is a structure similar to the LBA, aiming to produce a multidisciplinary synthesis and in-depth assessment of current knowledge about the Congo Basin.

The Libreville workshop resulted in a consensus on the priority issues for the CBSI's multidisciplinary scientific programme, which will soon be widely circulated as a concept note. These priority issues include:

- Understand the functioning of Central African ecosystems as a regional physical entity and their influence on the evolving Earth system.
- Analyse the impact of global, regional and local human activity on the ecosystems of the Congo Basin.
- To reconstruct the evolution of the ecosystems and climate of the Congo Basin and predicting their future evolution.
- To use scientific data to promote sustainable, climate-resilient land use and contribute to poverty eradication, economic prosperity and other sustainable development goals throughout the region.

Scientific meetings are planned until the end of the year to bring the OFV into line with the Congo Basin Science Initiative. The first was held in conjunction with the Three Basins Summit at the end of October 2023 in Brazzaville. The OFV's contribution to the SPCB is also being discussed at meetings with the SDSN.

2.3 The Libreville programming workshop

2.3.1 Objectives

The workshop was held from 22 to 24 November 2023 in Libreville, with the official opening at the Ministry of Water and Forests and the workshop itself on the premises of the Société d'Incubation Numérique du Gabon (SING SA). The event brought together some sixty Gabonese and French scientists (face-to-face and distance learning). Its overall aim was to co-construct the scientific and capacity-building aspects of the CP-Gabon, to understand the dynamics, diversity and functioning of Gabon's forest ecosystems,

² <https://congobasinscience.net/fr/>

quantifying climatic and anthropogenic pressures and feeding into the decision-making process (conservation, management, carbon, exploitation, etc.). The workshop used an innovative method of co-constructing the ideas proposed by the SING based on agile, lean startup and design thinking³ methods to produce OKRs (Objectives and Key Results). This method was essential to the workshop's running and significantly contributed to the quality of the results.

More specifically, the activities planned during the workshop were as follows:

- Present the functioning of the CPs and the expectations in terms of research and capacity development in Gabon, in particular within the framework of OFV and CBSI,
- Facilitate exchanges between Gabonese and French players, thematic area by thematic area, to define their effective involvement for the next four years,
- Identify the needs in terms of human resources, infrastructure and equipment required to implement the CP-Gabon's actions,
- Define together the intervention targets in Gabon to meet the scientific information needs of the CP-Gabon and the OFV,
- To programme the financial components for scientific research and capacity building necessary for implementing the CP-Gabon.
- To ratify implementing the OFV roadmap within the more general framework of the CP-Gabon.

2.3.2 Program

Day 1: Wednesday 22 November 2023	
Morning	
Conference room of the Ministry of Water and Forests	
07h30 – 08h45	Arrival and Registration of Participants
08h45 – 09h00	Installation of Participants
09h00 – 09h10	Arrival of the General Managers and Senior Officials
09h10 – 09h20	Arrival of Secretaries General of Ministries
09h20 – 09h30	Arrival of Cabinet Members
09h30 – 09h45	Arrival of Heads of Development Aid Organisations (UNDP, EU Delegation, AFD)
09h45 – 10h00	Arrival of the French Ambassador to Gabon
10h00 – 10h15	Arrival of the Members of the Government
10h15 – 11h00	Opening of the Workshop
	Presentation of the Challenges and Expectations of the Workshop
	<i>Gabonese side: Pr Alfred NGOMANDA</i>
	<i>French side: Dr Laurent DURIEUX</i>
	Opening speeches by
	His Excellency the Ambassador of France to Gabon
	Alexis LAMEK
	And
	The Minister of Water and Forests, in charge of Environmental Preservation, Climate and Human-Wildlife Conflict
	Colonel Maurice NTOSSUI ALLOGHO
11h15	Family photo
11h15 – 11h45	On-site cocktail for Officials

³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8ogLUTwyxsg>

11h45 – 12h40 Lunch for Permanent Participants at SING

Afternoon
SING SA offices

13h00 – 13h20 Installation of Participants and introductory remarks by SING SA
Technical presentations by Thematic Axes (**maximum 10 min per**

13h20 – 19h00 **presentation and 5 min for questions**) Overall Synthesis and
Formation of Groups

Coastal and marine
environments

French side

Dr François Le LOC'H

Gabonese side

M. Jean Hervé MVE BEH

French side

Dr Christophe PAUPY

Gabonese side

Dr Chimène NZE

One Health

Conservation of animal
biodiversity, umbrella
species, wildlife-
environment interaction,
management of human-
wildlife conflict (e.g.
elephants)

French side

Pr Sabrina KRIEF

Dr Marie SIGAUD

Gabonese side

Dr Etienne AKOMO OKOUE

Dr Stephan NTIE

Reliable carbon balance,
conservation of plant
biodiversity and land use

French side

Dr Jérôme CHAVE

Dr Nicolas BARBIER

Dr Martin SCWARTZ / Dr Aurélien DETRUCHIS

Dr Adeline FAYOLLE

Gabonese side

Dr Vincent MEDJIBE

Dr Conan Vassily OBAME

Pr. Rodrigue SAFOU TCHIAMA

Day 2: Thursday 23 November 2023

SING SA offices

07h00 – 07h30

Arrival of Participants

07h30 – 08h00:

Breakfast

08h00 – 12h00

Work in Thematic Group Commissions

12h00 – 12h45

Lunch break

13h00 – 18h45

Continuation of Committee work

Day 3: Friday 24 November 2023

SING SA offices

07h00 – 07h30

Arrival of Participants

07h30 – 08h00

Breakfast

08h00 – 12h30

Plenary presentation of Commission work

12h30 – 13h00

Lunch break

13h00 – 16h00

Preparation/Validation of the Roadmap

Concluding remarks by:

Dr Alain BILLAND

16h00 – 17h00

Dr Jean-François SOUSSANA

Pr. Stephan NTIE

Dr Donald MIDOKO IPONGA

Pr Alfred NGOMANDA

2.3.3 Report plan and supports

This report primarily highlights the work of the following four thematic groups, with the first two focusing specifically on OFV:

- **Groupe 1:** Accurate assessment of carbon emissions, plant biodiversity conservation and land use,
- **Groupe 2:** Conservation of animal biodiversity, umbrella species, wildlife-environment interaction, management of human-wildlife conflicts,
- **Groupe 3:** Promotion of sustainable value chains in the forest industry,
- **Group 4:** One Health.

The theme of "Coastal and marine environments" is dealt with briefly, as no group study has been conducted.

The report is accompanied by the presentations from the first day, available as a portfolio via a Wettransfer link.

3 Reliable carbon balance, conservation of plant biodiversity and land use

3.1 Introduction

This theme encompasses the interdependent pillars 1, 2 and 3 of acquiring fundamental knowledge, as well as the cross-cutting pillars 4 and 5 of communication, exchange and capacity building, as presented in the One Forest Vision (OFV) initiative at the One Forest Summit in Libreville in March 2023. More specifically, it deals in part with Pillar 1, which focuses on understanding forest carbon and biodiversity at the landscape scale, coordinated by Jérôme Chave of the CNRS and Sabrina Krief of the MNHN. Pillars 2 and 3 focus respectively on planning, with a large-scale carbon assessment of tropical forests coordinated by Philippe Ciais of the CEA, and on remote sensing and artificial intelligence applied right down to the tree, involving Philippe Ciais of the CEA and Frédéric Frappart of INRAE.

The challenges associated with this theme are as follows:

- Under certain conditions, forests can play a crucial role in capturing carbon from the atmosphere, thereby helping mitigate the impact of climate change, as highlighted in the Glasgow Declaration on Forests during COP 26. The signatory countries pledged to halt and reverse forest loss and land degradation by 2030,
- Current satellite missions to measure, report and verify (MRV) carbon stocks are based on indirect estimates of above-ground forest biomass,
- It is imperative to have a network of reference sites in the field⁴ ⁵, illustrated by the GEO-TREES initiative (<https://geo-trees.org>) and the African Tropical Rainforest

⁴ Labrière, N., Davies... & Chave, J. (2023). Toward a forest biomass reference measurement system for remote sensing applications. *Global Change Biology*, 29(3), 827-840.

⁵ Ploton, P., Mortier... & Gourlet-Fleury, S. (2020). A map of African humid tropical forest aboveground biomass derived from management inventories. *Scientific Data*, 7(1), 221.

Observatory Network (AfriTRON) for "intact" forests and the Tropical Managed Forests Observatory (TmFO, <https://tmfo.org/>) for exploited forests,

- Precise identification of trees and understory plants is essential for assessing carbon stocks and plant resources, considering the diversity of forest types present in the region⁶,
- Significant advances in plant identification methods, such as the Pl@ntNet initiative (<https://plantnet.org/>), now enable identification from photographs taken with a smartphone and the transfer of this knowledge to the general public,
- The production of high-resolution dynamic maps of aerial biomass globally is based on radar, optical and lidar satellite images. Recent advances in artificial intelligence and large-scale data processing mean that these images, calibrated with field observations, can be intelligently merged to create a near-real-time observatory of biomass, biodiversity and the degradation required to conserve tropical forests,
- To achieve the most reliable carbon balance possible, it is also necessary to propose improving estimates of carbon exchanges between the Earth and the atmosphere (vertical flows) by focusing on the accumulation of carbon in the landscape and its export through rivers (lateral flows). The aim is to bridge the gap between terrestrial and atmospheric approaches by promoting communication and synergy between research communities and making progress in assessing carbon budgets at the landscape scale⁷.

3.2 Objectives, activities and expected results

<p>General objectives</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To co-construct with the Gabonese scientific community several long-term reference research sites (supersites) with carbon and plant biodiversity monitoring capabilities to help improve fundamental knowledge of Gabon's forest ecosystems, • Assess the promise and limitations of existing technological solutions and stay at the forefront of advances in carbon and plant biodiversity monitoring, • Develop new approaches, in collaboration with users, to enable high spatial resolution monitoring over several years of land use, vegetation cover structure and carbon stocks in Gabon's forests, • To train Master's and PhD students, as well as early-career scientists, in new technologies through research, and to involve them in a practical, field-based approach ("boot-in-the-mud approach"), • Produce the information needed to define areas in addition to the existing ones to achieve 30% of crucial forest areas under protection.
<p>Keys activities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plant biodiversity: to contribute to a better understanding of the flora of Gabon (collection, curation and botanical revisions, participative and connected botanical approaches) and a better understanding of plant ecology (functional traits, phenological monitoring), • Reliable carbon balance: estimating carbon stocks from forest inventories, mapping carbon and estimating vertical and lateral carbon flows (experimental watershed approach),

⁶ Réjou-Méchain, M., Mortier, F., Bastin, J.F. et al. Unveiling African rainforest composition and vulnerability to global change. *Nature* **593**, 90–94 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03483-6>

⁷ Casas-Ruiz, J.P., Bodmer, P., Bona, K.A. et al. Integrating terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems to constrain estimates of land-atmosphere carbon exchange. *Nat Commun* **14**, 1571 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-37232-2>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land use: mapping land use and forest typology and mapping changes in land use and their causes.
Expected results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reliable reference data for the validation of global or regional forest carbon density maps based on standardized tools (protocols, encoding, ...), quality data and reference publications, long-term projects for field observatories, • Reliable dynamic maps of forest carbon density, enabling the quantification of carbon losses and their attribution to various natural or anthropogenic disturbances and of carbon gains from intact forests and secondary forests through regeneration, • The development of scientific and technological building blocks (AI, large-scale processing, remote sensing) in collaboration with the various project stakeholders, providing a reliable analytical framework for the preservation of tropical forests, • Long-term collaborations with research sites involved in the study of Gabon's forest ecosystems, • Intuitive, easy-to-use and free tropical botanical identification and training tools, • Messages for decision-makers and managers (concessions, protected areas), • Regarding capacity building: support for national research institutions + regionalization, young researchers anchored in an international network, field devices mobilized for training, reflection on masters/engineering programs (if required) and facilitation of student mobility.

3.3 Detailed activity plan

3.3.1 Social value proposition

Plant biodiversity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Services and goods (value chain), • Cultural value, • Biodiversity credits.
Carbon footprint	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hydroclimate, • Carbon credits, • Forest management and restoration of forest habitats, • Habitat matrix for remaining biodiversity, • To provide information and scientific data useful for the realization of a national land use plan (PNAT), • Make information available for the development and implementation of a National Natural Resources and Forestry Observation System (SNORNF), • Carry out carbon mapping on a national scale to define high-carbon stock areas, • Provide information to help achieve the 30x30 objectives, • Provide scientific and technical support to Gabonese policy on international negotiations such as the UNFCCC climate change negotiations.
Land use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional planning, • Reducing conflicts of use land management.

3.3.2 Beneficiaries

- **Gabonese society**, including urban and rural dwellers and indigenous peoples,
- **Knowledge** for managers, stakeholders (NGOs, companies), public authorities,
- **Better cooperation** for the academic and technical community,
- **Regional benefits:** opportunities for carbon and biodiversity credits, regional coordination on forest and climate issues,
- **Global benefit for the planet:** preservation of biodiversity and climate regulation.

3.3.3 Key activities

Plant biodiversity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge of the flora of Gabon (collection, curation and botanical revisions, participatory and connected botanical approaches) • Knowledge of plant ecology (functional traits, phenological monitoring)
Carbon footprint	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estimation of carbon stocks from forest inventories (plots, terrestrial lidar) • Carbon mapping (airborne lidar, satellite) • Carbon flows (flux towers, watershed approach)
Land use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mapping of land use and forest types • Mapping of land-use changes and identification of their causes

3.3.4 Key resources

Theme 1: Plant biodiversity		
Activities	Existing	Requests
1.1. Knowledge of the flora of Gabon	1.1.1 Collections of the National Herbarium of Gabon and local herbaria 1.1.2. Botanical inventory plots	1.1.1 Rehabilitation of the Gabonese National Herbarium Premises 1.1.2 Strengthening of collections (carpotheque); Support for local herbaria; Taxonomist position 1.1.3 Capacity building in participatory botanical science (Pl@ntNet)
1.2. Knowledge of plant ecology	1.2.1. Long-term ecology research supersites: Lopé, Ipassa, Moukabala 1.2.2. Long-term ecological knowledge	1.2.1 Functional ecology and ecophysiology laboratory 1.2.2 Three optical drones (phenology monitoring)
		Training: 4 PhDs, several Master's degrees, training for field staff (including MOOCs), support for curriculum revision Data strategy

Theme 2: Carbon footprint		
Activities	Existing	Requests
2.1. Estimation of carbon stocks from forest inventories	2.1.1 Inventory of Natural resources (IRN) 2.1.2 Supersites 2.1.3 Regional allometries (PREREDD+)	2.1.1. Field research capacity building (vehicles, encoding tools) 2.1.2. Scanning equipment (TLS, drones) Carbon analysis processing lines 2.1.3 Strengthening IRN teams 2.1.4 Micrometeorology sensors and weather stations

2.2. Carbon mapping	2.2.1 AGEOS expertise 2.2.2 Pre-existing maps 2.2.3 Lidar flights	2.2.1. Airborne lidar scans of supersites and other areas of interest
2.3. Carbon flows	2.3.1 Watershed approach on the Ogooué	2.3.1 Water, soil and rock laboratory 2.3.2. Turbulent flow tower
		Training: 4 PhDs, several Master's degrees, training for field staff (including MOOCs), support for curriculum revision Data strategy

Theme 3: Land use		
Activities	Existing	Requests
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3.1. Mapping land use and forest typology 3.2. Mapping land-use changes and their causes 	3. AGEOS infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3.1. High-performance computing resources 3.2. Sovereignty-compliant data storage facilities 3.3. Enhanced image analysis capabilities (deep learning) 3.4. Strengthening AGEOS personnel
		Training: 3 PhDs, several Master's degrees, training for field staff (including MOOCs), support for curriculum revision Data strategy

3.3.5 Key partners

Gabon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CENAREST (IRET, Herbar National du Gabon, IRAF), AGEOS, ANPN, USTM, UOB, ENEF
France	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CEA, CNRS, IRD, CIRAD, INRAE, MNHN

3.3.6 Relationships

- Strengthen and create networks of relationships between establishments, institutions and stakeholders (technical ministries, government organizations, development donors -CAFI, EU, AFD, FFEM, World Bank, etc.-, private sector, non-governmental organizations, think tanks, civil society, communities, biodiversity and carbon consultancies),
- Promote transparency in collaborations,
- Establish and maintain long-term win/win relationships of trust with local communities,
- Organization of workshops for reflection, exchange and feedback on targeted themes.

3.3.7 Channels

- Obtain the necessary research authorizations,
- Establish partnership agreements with local, national and international institutions and players,
- Establish a **communication and digital action plan** to consider essential events, deadlines and opportunities to present results. The plan will be multi-layered:
 - Exchanges to promote knowledge transfer (workshops) and international and sub-regional mobility,
 - Scientific valorization (publications, scientific communications, symposia),
 - Public awareness and outreach (media and other audiences),
 - Communication for decision-makers (summary reports and recommendations).

3.3.8 Cost structure

At present, it is difficult to assess the cost structure of the CP Gabon in light of the elements at our disposal. However, as far as the OFV theme is concerned, the cost structure will depend on several factors, such as the nature of the activities, the duration of the project (here dimensioned for 04 years), the resources required, and the specific policies of the donor(s) (MESR and MEAE) granting the subsidy. The general cost structure of the "Reliable carbon balance, plant biodiversity conservation and land use" theme could be as follows

Staff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Salaries and benefits for principal investigators, collaborators and support staff. • Training and professional development costs (capacity building for researchers, students, engineers and technicians, postdocs, etc.). • Recruitment of PhDs, postdocs, IT and project managers.
Equipment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Costs of purchasing or leasing specialized equipment required for research.
Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Costs of renovating existing laboratories and research stations (e.g. supersites).
Consumables	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Laboratory materials, office supplies, chemicals, etc.
Travel and accommodation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Travel to conferences, meet collaborators or conduct field or laboratory work.
Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication costs, including access to databases, specialized journals, software subscriptions, etc.
Administrative expenses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project administration overheads include management costs, legal services, accounting services, etc.
Subcontracting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Costs associated with the purchase of specialized services (e.g. SING SA).
Diffusion of results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Costs associated with publication of research results, organization of conferences, etc.
Evaluation and follow-up	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expenses related to evaluating the project and monitoring its progress.

3.3.9 Impacts

Impact 1:	Value Chain Optimization for Services and Goods	Improved management of natural resources to maximize the production of goods and services, promoting sustainable and efficient use of ecosystems.
Impact 2:	Preservation and Promotion of Cultural Value	Support for conserving cultural and spiritual values linked to biodiversity, strengthening cultural identity and promoting respect for nature.
Impact 3:	Contribution to the implementation and development of Biodiversity Credits	Valuation and monetary recognition of biodiversity, encouraging the conservation and restoration of ecosystems through financial incentives.
Impact 4:	Contributions to the fight against climate change	Use of information to generate carbon credits and promote sustainable management practices, thus actively contributing to the fight against climate change.
Impact 5:	Forest Management, Habitat Restoration and Land Use Planning	Improving forest management practices, habitat restoration and land-use planning to reduce conflicts of use and ensure sustainable use of land resources.

These impacts represent critical aspects of the actions undertaken, ranging from maximizing the value chain of services and goods to cultural preservation, providing information concerning the valuation of carbon credits and/or biodiversity, the contribution to climate control and the sustainable management of forest ecosystems and the territory. They will:

- Provide essential information for the National Land Allocation Commission (CNAT),
- Support the development and implementation of a National Natural Resources and Forestry Observation System (SNORNF),
- Mapping carbon on a national scale to identify areas with high carbon stocks,
- Provide crucial information to meet 30x30 biodiversity conservation targets,
- Provide scientific and technical support for international negotiations, particularly climate change, under the UNFCCC.

3.4 Prioritization

The following table presents a three-year plan to implement key deliverables related to plant biodiversity, carbon footprint and land use. In the short-term, actions include support for local herbaria, setting up a functional ecology laboratory, acquiring optical drones, training PhD students and developing a data management plan. In the medium term, the focus shifts to rehabilitating the National Herbarium's premises, strengthening participatory science skills, collection development and data management. Finally, the long-term focus is on building research capacity, airborne lidar scans, HPC equipment,

image analysis skills, and long-term data management, with ongoing support for training and revision of teaching curricula.

Key deliverables	Short-term: Implemented within the next three years	Medium-term: Scheduled for implementation between years three and six	Long-term: Planned for implementation beyond the next six years
Plant biodiversity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operation: Support for local herbaria • Infrastructures: Functional Ecology and Ecophysiology Laboratory (CENAREST) • Equipment: Three optical drones (phenology monitoring) • Training: PhD (n=2), master's scholarships (n=4), field actors (including MOOC) • Data strategy: Data management plan, data management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infrastructures: Rehabilitation of the premises of the National Herbarium of Gabon • Personnel: Taxonomist position • Reinforcement of botanical participatory science skills (PI@ntNet) • Training: PhD (n=2), master's scholarships (n=4), field actors (including MOOC) • Data strategy: Data management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operation: Strengthening of collections (carpotheque) • Training: Master's scholarships (n=3), field actors (including MOOC) • Workshops: Support for curriculum revision • Data strategy: Data management
Carbon footprint	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equipment: Enhanced field search capabilities (vehicles, encoding tools) • Equipment: scan (TLS, drones) • Personnel: Reinforcement of IRN teams • Equipment: Micrometeorological sensors and weather stations • Services: Airborne lidar scans on supersites and other areas of interest • Infrastructure: Water, soil and rock laboratory (CENAREST) • Training: PhD (n=2), master's scholarships (n=4), field actors (including MOOC) • Data strategy: Data management plan, data management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Services: Carbon analysis processing lines • Services: Airborne lidar scans of supersites and other areas of interest • Infrastructures: Turbulent flow tower • Training: PhD (n=2), master's scholarships (n=4), field actors (including MOOC) • Data strategy: Long-term data management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equipment: Enhanced field search capabilities (vehicles, encoding tools) • Services: Airborne lidar scans of supersites and other areas of interest • Training: Master's scholarships (n=3), field actors (including MOOC) • Workshops: Support for curriculum revision • Data strategy: Long-term data management

- **Equipment:** High-Performance Computing
 - **Training:** Enhanced image analysis capabilities (deep learning)
 - **Personnel:** Reinforcement of AGEOS teams
 - **Training:** PhD (n=1), Master's scholarships (n=3), field actors (including MOOC)
 - **Data strategy:** Data management plan, data management
- **Equipment:** Sovereignty-compliant data storage facilities
 - **Training:** PhD (n=1), Master's scholarships (n=3), field actors (including MOOC)
 - **Data strategy:** Long-term data management
- **Training:** PhD (n=1), Master's scholarships (n=3), field actors (including MOOC)
 - **Workshops:** Support for curriculum revision
 - **Data strategy:** Long-term data management

3.5 Budget estimates

The following budget estimate concerns only four-year OFV activities, including MESR and MEAE allocations.

	Equipment	Operation	Personnel	Total (€)
1. Plant biodiversity	350 000	380 000	256 000	986 000
○ 1.1. Knowledge of the flora of Gabon		270 000		270 000
○ 1.2. Knowledge of plant ecology	350 000	50 000		400 000
○ 1.3. Training		40 000	256 000	296 000
○ 1.4. Data strategy		20 000		20 000
2. Carbon footprint	580 000	380 000	256 000	1 216 000
○ 2.1. Estimating carbon stocks from forest inventories	340 000			340 000
○ 2.2. Carbon mapping	240 000	200 000		440 000
○ 2.3. Carbon flows				
○ 2.4. Training		40 000	256 000	296 000
○ 2.5. Data strategy		140 000		140 000
3. Land use		180 000	356 000	536 000
○ 3.1. Mapping land use and forest typology				
○ 3.2. Mapping land-use changes and their causes			100 000	100 000
○ 3.3. Training		40 000	256 000	296 000
○ 3.4. Data strategy		140 000		140 000
4. Gestion et communication			200 000	200 000
○ 4.1. VI			100 000	100 000
○ 4.2. Expatriates			100 000	100 000
Total	930 000	940 000	1 068 000	2 938 000

3.6 List of participants

Name	Institution	Position	E-mail	Presential/Visio
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1	Guy Serge Bignoumba	UOB		gsbignoumba@yahoo.fr	P
2	Quentin Moundoung Mavouroulo u	CENAREST	IRET	moundounga@yahoo.fr	P
3	Vincent Midjibé	ANPN		medjibe@gmail.com	P
4	Archange Boupoya	CENAREST	IPHAMETRA	boupoyaclay@hotmail.com	P
5	Franck Rodrigue Olouo Ambounda	CENAREST	IRET	rodfranck@hotmail.com	P
6	Raymonde Mboma	CENAREST	IRET	belleorchidey@yahoo.fr	P
7	Rodrigue Safou Tchiamama	USTM	Pr.	rodriguesafoutchiamama@gmail.com	P
8	Conan Vassily Obame	AGEOS	AGEOS	obameconanvassily@gmail.com	P
9	St Bickolard Mabicka Iwangou	CENAREST	IRT	saintbickolard@yahoo.fr	P
10	Prudence Yombiyeni	CENAREST	IRT	prudence_yom@yahoo.fr	P
11	Raissa Mouketa	Tropicalthèque		raissamouketa@gmail.com	P
12	Jérôme Chave	CNRS	UMR EDB	jerome.chave@univ-tlse3.fr	P
13	Nicolas Barbier	IRD	UMR AMAP	nicolas.barbier@ird.fr	P
14	Adeline Fayolle	CIRAD	UR Forêts et Société	adeline.fayolle@ulg.ac.be	P
15	Martin Schwartz	CEA	LSCE	martin.schwartz@lsce.ipsl.fr	P
16	Aurelien de Truchis	KAYROS	KAYROS	a.detruichis@kayros.com	P

4 Conservation of animal biodiversity, umbrella species, wildlife-environment interaction, management of human-wildlife conflict

4.1 Introduction

This theme addresses the part of Pillar 1, coordinated by Jérôme Chave of CNRS and Sabrina Krief of MNHN, dealing with animal biodiversity, with interactions under cross-cutting pillars 4 and 5 of communication, exchange and capacity building, as presented in the One Forest Vision (OFV) initiative at the One Forest Summit in Libreville in March 2023.

Biodiversity and the many ecosystem functions and services it underpins are undergoing significant and often rapid change on a global scale. The complex issues of knowledge and governance linked to understanding, monitoring and conserving animal biodiversity are central to preserving the forests of the Congo Basin, which contain biodiversity as exceptional as it is essential to the proper functioning of these ecosystems. What's more, achieving the 30 x 30 objectives set by Gabon requires an ambitious roadmap, meaningfully integrating all relevant local players, particularly local communities. Considering the scientific aspects and capacity-building of the Country Packages between France and Gabon is an essential step in this direction.

The working group dedicated to animal biodiversity initiated the development of a roadmap integrating the priorities set by the Gabonese state. Group members included Gabonese representatives from the Agence nationale des parcs nationaux, the Institut de recherche en écologie tropicale, the Institut de Recherches Agronomiques et Forestières, as well as government representatives, notably from the Ministry of Waters and Forests, responsible for environmental preservation, climate and human-wildlife conflict. French institutions were represented by the Université Bourgogne Franche-Comté, the Museum National d'Histoire Naturelle and CIRAD. International NGOs were represented by WCS and Panthera, and the private sector by Okala. These collegial exchanges led to the elaboration of six primary objectives: the assessment and monitoring of animal biodiversity, the study of the contribution of animal biodiversity to the functioning of ecosystems and their contribution to the local economy, sustainable and peaceful human-wildlife coexistence, the involvement of local communities, the reinforcement of human and material capacities and, finally, the management, storage and valorization of data.

4.2 Objectives, activities and expected results

General objectives GO	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• GO1: Assessment and monitoring of animal biodiversity• GO2: Contribution of animal diversity to ecosystem functioning and ecosystem services• GO3: Sustainable human-wildlife coexistence• GO4: Involvement of local communities• GO5: Human and material capacity building• GO6: Data management, storage and valorization (priority, sharing, valorization, decision support, economic valorization... to be specified in the sub-objectives)
Key activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Assessment and monitoring of animal biodiversity: Inventory and further research on animal biodiversity and ecosystem services; development/implementation of standardized indicators and monitoring,

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contribution of biodiversity to ecosystem services: Studies of interactions and interaction networks; establishment of mechanisms for the contribution of biodiversity to the local economy, • Sustainable human-wildlife coexistence: Inventory of human-wildlife conflicts and integration of human aspects; study of elephant behaviour about anthropogenic changes and conflicts; implementation and testing of mitigation and awareness-raising measures; creation of a national authority on human-wildlife conflict, • Involvement of local communities: Study and valorization of traditional knowledge and uses and human-wildlife interactions; co-construction of monitoring and management of animal biodiversity; proposals for rules to support the transfer of responsibility for managing and governance, • Strengthening human and material capacities: Taking stock of short- and long-term needs, setting up continuing education programs, focusing on university degree programs, reinforcing collaborative networks, drawing up/implementing a plan for strengthening and sustaining equipment and infrastructure, • Data management, storage and enhancement: Carrying out an inventory; setting up a mechanism for sharing existing data; developing a national strategy; designing training courses; and creating infrastructure.
Expected results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better understanding of animal biodiversity as a driver of ecosystem functioning and ecosystem services in the context of climate change, • Implications, appropriation and improvement of living conditions for local communities, • Numerical reinforcement and increased skills of teams in these areas, • Sustainable and peaceful human-wildlife coexistence, • Conservation in protected areas and sustainable management with the support of local communities, • Increase cutting-edge scientific production on forest ecosystems and outstanding international visibility (regional centre of excellence). • Availability, updating and storage of high-quality data on animal biodiversity for decision-making and cutting-edge research.

4.3 Detailed activity plan

4.3.1 Social value proposition

- Compiling and making available data (sovereignty, quality and sustainability) on animal biodiversity for conservation, management, decision support and ecosystem services (**GO1 to GO6**),
- Support for the development of a sustainable economy based on animal biodiversity (e.g. ecotourism, sustainable exploitation of wildlife) (**GO2 and GO4**),
- Sustainable human-wildlife coexistence (**GO3**),
- Recognition of traditional knowledge and involvement of local communities in the monitoring, management and governance of animal biodiversity (**GO4**),
- Qualified and autonomous material and human capacities for research, teaching and socio-economic actors (**GO5**).

4.3.2 Beneficiaries

- National and international political decision-makers,
- Local communities and representatives of civil society,
- Public and private socio-economic actors involved in sustainable development,
- National and international scientific communities,
- Administrative actors and public institutions.

4.3.3 Key activities

<p>GO1</p> <p>Assessment and monitoring of animal biodiversity</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carry out an inventory; identify knowledge needs (essential biodiversity/EBV variables, pressures, local knowledge, connectivity) and the forces at work, • Organise inventories and additional research, particularly in existing and potential protected areas, as part of Objective 30, • Define indicators and monitoring methods, standardise them and select long-term reference sites, • Implement standardised monitoring.
<p>GO2</p> <p>Contribution of animal diversity to ecosystem functioning and ecosystem services</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Studying interactions and interaction networks (pollination, seed dispersal, etc.) and their impact on geochemical cycles and carbon sequestration in the context of climate change, • Establish mechanisms for contributing biodiversity to a sustainable economy: sustainable ecotourism, NTFPs, certificates, sustainable green financing, and food security (safe and sustainable consumption of bushmeat/fishery resources about the risk of zoonoses).
<p>GO3</p> <p>Sustainable and peaceful human-wildlife coexistence</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Draw up an inventory of knowledge on the conflicts and species concerned (crop damage, human mortality), • Improve understanding of the behavioural ecology of elephants (and other species) and the influence of anthropogenic changes, • Gain a better understanding of the human aspects of conflicts (socio-economic data, SHS dimensions, mitigation measures, traditional knowledge), • Propose mitigation and awareness-raising measures and assess their effectiveness, • Set up a national body to monitor human-wildlife conflict.
<p>GO4</p> <p>Involvement of local communities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Studying and promoting traditional knowledge and practices, • Gain a better understanding of the dynamics of human-wildlife interactions (hunting/fishing, other subsistence practices, cultural and cultic practices, poaching) in a context of global change, • To co-construct (from design to implementation) the monitoring and management of animal biodiversity, particularly in protected areas (national, community), • Propose rules based on scientific knowledge to support the transfer of responsibilities in terms of management and governance (e.g. community protected areas, management contracts).
<p>GO5</p> <p>Human and material capacity building</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Take stock of short- and long-term needs, • Set up continuing education courses for professionals (including new techniques and certificates) and recognise the value of experience gained through certified recognition, • Focus university degree courses on the sustainable management of animal biodiversity (LMD, DU), • Initiate discussions on the emergence of an institute or centre of excellence for forestry with a regional vocation, including a museum and collection conservation component, • Strengthen multidisciplinary collaboration networks and North/South and South/South communications (mobility, student co-supervision, scientific meetings) with existing regional networks (e.g. R2FAC), • Draw up and implement a plan to strengthen and ensure the sustainability of equipment and infrastructure.

GO6 Data management, storage and exploitation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carry out an inventory (structures hosting data and data sources), • Set up a mechanism for sharing existing data (framework agreement, convention, etc.), • Develop a national data centralisation and hosting strategy (sovereign storage method, medium- and long-term solution), • Create an infrastructure and design training courses for data management, storage and exploitation.
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4.3.4 Key resources

Needs	Expectations
Human resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recruitment and capacity-building of national researchers, technicians and field staff in the field of ecology and social and human sciences, • Increasing project management capacity (administrative management team), • Recruitment and supervision of students (LMD), • Strengthening and stimulating international cooperation in the field of research, • Training research and development support staff (extensive data management, artificial intelligence, new technologies), • Technical staff to ensure the durability of equipment (electronics training).
Operating resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small items of equipment (solar panels, field equipment), fuel, consumables, insurance, etc, • Depreciation and maintenance costs for equipment (laboratories, etc.), • Running premises costs (electricity, internet, office equipment, etc.).
Acquisition of equipment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New technology sensors, laboratory equipment, • Updating (monitoring and renewal) of existing equipment (e.g. GPS collars, photo traps, acoustic recorders, laboratory equipment), • Computer equipment, • Field vehicles, • Strengthen the data storage system (at the technical ministries and CENAREST, AGEOS and ANPN) and analysis capabilities (dedicated workstations).
Research buildings and infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthen existing infrastructure at supersites (La Lopé, Ipassa, Moukalaba), • Develop the capacity of the camps (Loango, Batéké, Mont Crystal) and identify potential sites for new camps and research stations, • Maintain and develop analysis laboratories (IRET, ANPN, USTM, CERMEL, CIRMF).
Field missions/Field deployment/Field Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Field missions (collaring, sample collection, deployment of sensors, data collection, deployment of standardised protocols, etc.), • Long-term storage and analysis of biological samples in national laboratories.

4.3.5 Key partners

Gabon	CENAREST, AGEOS, ANPN, national research and higher education establishments (USTM, ENEF, UOB, CIRMF, CERMEL, etc.), private socio-economic players, national technical ministries, community associations, etc.
France	French research and higher education establishments (CEA, CIRAD, CNRS, INRAE, IRD, MNHN, etc.), French technical ministries

4.3.6 Relationships

- Strengthening and creating networks of relationships between establishments, institutions and stakeholders,
- Promoting transparency in collaborations,
- Establishing and maintaining long-term win/win relationships of trust with communities,
- Organising workshops for reflection, exchange and feedback on targeted themes.

4.3.7 Channels

- Establish partnership agreements with local, national and international institutions and players,
- Knowledge transfer and exchanges (to be specified, mobility, etc.),
- Scientific promotion (publications, scientific communication, conferences),
- Awareness-raising and popularisation (media and other audiences),
- Summary reports and recommendations for decision-makers,
- Organisation of workshops for discussion, exchange and feedback on targeted themes,
- Donors.

4.3.8 Cost structure

The cost structure can be organised around the following points, depending on the general objectives:

- Compiling and making available data (sovereignty, quality and sustainability) on animal biodiversity for conservation, management, decision support and ecosystem services (GO1 to GO6),
- Infrastructure renovation,
- Salary mass,
- Support for the development of a sustainable economy based on animal biodiversity (e.g. ecotourism, sustainable use of wildlife) (GO2 and GO4),
- Sustainable human-wildlife coexistence (GO3),
- Recognition of traditional knowledge and involvement of local communities in the monitoring, management and governance of animal biodiversity (GO4),
- Qualified and autonomous material and human capacities for research, teaching and socio-economic actors (GO5).

4.3.9 Impacts

- Better understanding of animal biodiversity as a driving force behind the functioning of ecosystems and ecosystem services in the context of climate change,
- Implications, ownership and improved living conditions for local communities,
- Increased cutting-edge scientific production on forest ecosystems and enhanced international visibility (regional centre of excellence),

- Numerical reinforcement and skills enhancement for teams working on these themes,
- Sustainable and peaceful coexistence between man and wildlife,
- Conservation in national parks and sustainable management with the support of local communities,
- Availability, updating and storage of high-quality data on animal biodiversity to support decision-making and cutting-edge research.

4.4 Prioritization

Key deliverables	Short-term: Implemented within the next three years	Medium-term: Scheduled for implementation between years three and six	Long-term: Planned for implementation beyond the next six years
Assessment and monitoring of animal biodiversity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Taking stock and identifying needs • Define indicators and tracking methods and standardise them • Choose long-term reference sites 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organise inventories and additional research • Implement standardised monitoring • Define indicators and tracking methods and standardise them 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement standardised monitoring
Ecosystem functioning and ecosystem services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Studying interactions and networks of interactions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishing mechanisms for the contribution of biodiversity to a sustainable economy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishing mechanisms for the contribution of biodiversity to a sustainable economy
Coexistence Homme-faune durable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To draw up an inventory of knowledge on the conflicts and species concerned • Improve understanding of the behavioural ecology of elephants (and other species) and the influence of anthropogenic changes • Gain a better understanding of the human aspects of conflicts (socio-economic data, SHS dimensions, mitigation measures, traditional knowledge) • Create a national body to monitor human-wildlife conflict 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve understanding of the behavioural ecology of elephants (and other species) and the influence of anthropogenic changes. • Propose mitigation and awareness-raising measures and evaluate their effectiveness 	

Involvement of local communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Studying and promoting traditional knowledge Gain a better understanding of the dynamics of human-wildlife interactions (hunting/fishing, other subsistence practices, cultural and cultic practices, poaching) in a context of global change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Co-constructing (from design to implementation) the monitoring and management of animal biodiversity, particularly in protected areas (national, community) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Propose rules based on scientific knowledge to support the transfer of management and governance responsibilities (e.g. community, protected areas, management contracts, etc.)
Human and material capacity building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Take stock of short- and long-term needs Introduce ongoing training for professionals (including new techniques and certificates) and recognise the value of experience gained through certified recognition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Focus university degree courses on the sustainable management of animal biodiversity (LMD, DU) Initiate reflection on the emergence of an institute or centre of excellence on forestry with a regional vocation, including a museum component and collection conservation. Draw up and implement a plan to strengthen and ensure the sustainability of equipment and infrastructure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strengthen multidisciplinary collaboration networks and North/South and South/South communications (mobility, student co-supervision, scientific meetings) with existing regional networks (e.g. R2FAC)
Data management, storage and exploitation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Carry out an inventory (structures hosting data and data sources) Set up a mechanism for sharing existing data (framework agreement, convention, etc.) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop a national data centralisation and hosting strategy (sovereign storage mode, medium- and long-term solution) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Create an infrastructure and design training courses for data management, storage and enhancement

4.5 Budget estimates

It has not yet been possible to estimate the budget, and the costs have yet to be added to the table below, which lists and structures the main objectives and activities to be implemented:

Objectives/Activities	Human resources	Operation	Material	Infrastructures	Field missions
1 Assessing and monitoring animal biodiversity					
1.1 Taking stock and identifying needs					

1.2 Define indicators and monitoring methods and standardise them.					
1.3 Organise inventories and additional research, particularly in existing and potential protected areas within the framework of objective 30 X 30.					
1.4. Implement standardised monitoring					
2. Contribution of animal diversity to ecosystem functioning and ecosystem services					
2.1. Studying interactions and interaction networks (pollination, seed dispersal, etc.) and their impact on geochemical cycles and carbon sequestration in the context of climate change.					
2.2 Establishing mechanisms for biodiversity to contribute to a sustainable economy.					
3. Sustainable and peaceful coexistence between man and wildlife					
3.1 Taking stock of knowledge on conflicts and the species concerned					
3.2. Improve knowledge of the behavioural ecology of elephants (and other species) and the influence of anthropogenic changes					
3.3. Human aspects of conflicts (socio-economic data, SHS dimensions, mitigation measures, traditional knowledge)					
3.4. Mitigation measures, awareness-raising and evaluation of effectiveness					
3.5. National monitoring body on human-wildlife conflict					
4. Implications for local communities					
4.1 Studying and promoting traditional knowledge					
4.2 Gain a better understanding of the dynamics of human-wildlife interactions (hunting/fishing, other subsistence practices, cultural and cultic practices, poaching) in a context of global change.					
4.3. Co-construct (from design to implementation) the monitoring and management of animal biodiversity, particularly in protected areas (national, community).					
4.4. Propose rules based on scientific knowledge to support the transfer of responsibilities in terms of management and governance (e.g. community protected areas, management contracts)					
5. Strengthening human and material capacities					
5.1. Take stock of short- and long-term needs					
5.2. Introduce ongoing training for professionals (including new techniques certificates) and enhance the value of acquired experience through certified recognition.					
5.3. Focus university degree courses on the sustainable management of animal biodiversity (LMD, DU).					
5.4. initiate discussions on the emergence of an institute or centre of excellence for forestry with a regional vocation, including a museum component and collections conservation.					
5.5. Strengthen multi-disciplinary collaboration networks and North/South and South/South communications (mobility, student co-supervision, scientific meetings) with existing regional networks (e.g. R2FAC).					
5.6. Draw up and implement a plan to strengthen and ensure the sustainability of equipment and infrastructure					
6. Management, storage and use of data					
6.1. Carry out an inventory (structures hosting data and data sources)					

6.2. Set up a mechanism for sharing existing data (framework agreement, convention, etc.)					
6.3. Develop a national strategy for centralising and hosting data (sovereign storage method, medium- and long-term solution).					
6.4. Create an infrastructure and design training courses for data management, storage and exploitation					

4.6 List of participants

	Name	Institution	Fonction	E-mail	Presential /Visio
1	Stephan Ntié	ANPN	Conseiller scientifique	stephanntie@yahoo.fr	P
2	Christopher Orbell	PANTHERA		corbell@panthera.org	P
3	Etienne François Akomo Okoué	CENAREST	IRET	akomookoue1977@gmail.com	P
4	Donald Midoko Iponga	CENAREST	IRET	dmiponga@gmail.com	P
5	Stéphanie Bourgeois	ANPN	ANPN	stephbourgeois_@hotmail.com	P
6	David Lehmann	OKALA	ARISE	david.lehmann@okala.io	P
7	Jimmy Franck Nzomba			jimmy.mentorbushmeatfr@gmail.com	P
8	Blaise Rollinat Mboye	CENAREST	IRAF	mblaiseerollinat@gmail.com	P
9	Gaspard Abitsi	WCS		gabitsi@wcs.org	P
10	Quentin Moundoung Mavouroulou	CENAREST	IRET	moundoungaq@yahoo.fr	P
11	Alain Billand	CIRAD	Dir.	alain.billand@cirad.fr	P
12	Marie Sigaud	MNHN		sigaud.m@gmail.com	P
13	François Brétagnolle	U. Bourgogne		francois.bretagnolle@u-bourgogne.fr	P
14	Steeve Ngama	CENAREST	IRET	ngama.steeve@gmail.com	P
15	Jean Felicien Liwouwou	CENAREST	IRAF/DGEA	jean_feli@yahoo.fr	P
16	Tierry Diop Bineni	CENAREST	IRET	diopbinenithierry01@gmail.com	P

17	Guy Serge Bignoumba	UOB		sergemib@yahoo.fr	P
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5 Promoting sustainable value chains in the forestry industry

5.1 Introduction

In 2010, the Gabonese government imposed an obligation to process all logs locally, leading to increased waste production from the wood industry. This biomass, comprising sawdust, shavings, processing residues and related forestry products, represents considerable volumes. In 2020, the ITTO (International Tropical Timber Organisation) estimated the volume of wood by-products from wood processing in Gabon at 1,275,000 m³, representing a material yield of 49.4%. Little is made of these by-products locally.

At the same time, Gabon's non-timber forest products (NTFPs), such as fibres, resins, mushrooms and fruits, remain primarily underexploited. The Gabonese authorities, in collaboration with the French Ambassador for the Environment, have made promoting a sustainable timber industry one of the priorities of the Country Package Gabon.

However, limited knowledge of wood resources and NTFPs is hampering the development of this value chain. The "Wood and NTFP Value Chain" pillar aims to remedy this shortcoming by implementing a research and development strategy. This initiative, supported by Gabonese and French institutions, aims to add value to untapped bioresources, notably logging waste, industrial wood scraps and NTFPs.

Applications envisaged include the manufacture of high-value-added products such as composite materials, the extraction of bio-sourced molecules for cosmetics and the formulation of natural pesticides, and the valorization of NTFPs as nutritious foods.

Despite scientific advances, experts point to gaps in research, notably due to the sheer size of the forests, difficult access and lack of global investment. The pillar draws on the expertise of the Laboratoire de Recherche et de Valorisation du Matériau Bois in Gabon, reinforced by collaborations with French institutions.

In conclusion, the success of this NCFP pillar depends on solid scientific support, an interdisciplinary approach and the strengthening of national capacities to ensure the sustainable valorization of logging and timber industry wastes, as well as economically undervalued NTFPs.

5.2 Objectives, activities and expected results

Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop the sustainable value chain for wood and non-timber forest products (NTFPs) on an industrial scale; Increase research & development and transfer activities to companies.
Key activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Set up initial training programs to support the development of the pillar; Build the capacity of research technicians and engineers;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Produce composite materials and extract high-value-added molecules from resins and related products from the wood and NTFP industries.
Expected results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase Gabon's industrial capacity and enter new markets (particleboard, cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, organic food, etc.); • Create new jobs and combat youth unemployment in particular; • Improve the quality of research in wood and NTFP sciences; • Strengthen research cooperation between Gabon and France.

5.3 Detailed activity plan

5.3.1 Social value proposition

The social value proposition for the development of the sustainable timber and NTFP industry value chain is based on the following principles:

- **Added value for society and job diversity at all levels:** Effective implementation of this pillar will generate significant added value for Gabonese society, creating new jobs spread across several sectors of activity such as collection, waste sorting, new product implementation, and marketing. This will help to diversify employment opportunities at various levels.
- **Optimization and valorization of by-products and secondary species:** The optimization of processes for valorizing by-products from forestry and the timber industry will be based on in-depth scientific knowledge of the waste generated by species with high commercial value. Selective sorting and the study of the properties of waste from different species, including those little exploited locally, will play a key role in this optimization. The valorization of by-products will focus on promising sectors, favouring transferable technologies and uncomplicated appropriation.
- **Training:** Training is a fundamental aspect of this social proposition. Mastering the processes of the sustainable wood and NTFP value chain requires solid initial training and upgrading existing players' skills to adapt to new jobs. This pillar aims to train technicians, engineers, PhDs and high-level managers, strengthening local skills and fostering a skilled workforce.

5.3.2 Beneficiaries

Les bénéficiaires prioritaires de ce pilier "Chaînes de valeur durable de l'industrie du bois et des PFNL" se répartissent dans différentes catégories, mettant en avant les acteurs clés de manière suivante:

- **The job market, especially young people:** The creation of new and diversified jobs focusing on young people aims to reduce the high unemployment rate, reaching up to 40% of the working population in Gabon. This pillar thus offers significant employment opportunities for this category of society.
- **Socio-economic operators and inter-professional structures in the forest-wood sector:** Companies and inter-professional structures such as UFIGA, SIAG, FGBSP and GZES, Nkok will benefit from the increased integration of the sustainable wood and NTFP value chain into the national economy. This will strengthen the overall performance of the forestry and timber sector.
- **The State:** Public revenues generated by the activities of this value chain will contribute to strengthening the sector's performance while supporting the State

through an increase in Gross Domestic Product (GDP), thus consolidating its financial resources.

- **The national scientific community:** Researchers and scientists will have direct access to new scientific and technological data, notably on the technical properties of wood in reconstituted materials and the identification of new molecules with high potential in fields such as cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, adhesives and agri-food. The industrial-scale implementation of research results will strengthen interactions between research and development.
- **Development NGOs:** Non-governmental organizations specializing in waste management and collection and organising short valorization circuits for other by-products will be active beneficiaries. Their expertise can be used in the sustainable wood and NTFP value chain, contributing to sustainable practices and efficient waste management.

5.4 Key activities

The effectiveness of the sustainable wood value chain will positively impact related sectors, reducing industrial waste, encouraging the development of biomass facilities, and promoting environmentally responsible approaches such as the circular economy and eco-design. The implementation of the sustainable value chain for the wood and NTFP industry in Gabon will be based on educational, research and transfer activities, encompassing:

5.4.1.1 Teaching activities

- **Reinforcement of existing courses:**
 - Reinforce fundamental knowledge of wood and NTFPs.
 - Integrate industrial technologies into existing training courses.
- **Revision of the training offer:**
 - Adapt existing courses at ENEF, ENSET, ITO and USTM.
 - Introduce new courses to meet the needs of industry professionals.

5.4.1.2 Research activities

- **Operational knowledge in Gabon:**
 - Expertise in wood anatomy, microstructure and quality.
 - Expertise in the natural durability, microbiology and mycology of wood.
 - Chemistry of extractives and lignocellulosic materials.
 - Analysis of the physics and mechanics of wood and composites.
- **Strengthening existing capacities:**
 - Upgrading of equipment in existing laboratories.
 - Strengthening the skills of research technicians and engineers.

5.4.1.3 Complementary activities

- **Optimization of related activities:**
 - Setting up an efficient system for collecting, sorting, grinding and drying co-products.

- Development of the circular economy and promotion of eco-design.

5.4.2 Key resources

The following table summarizes the key resources required to establish a sustainable wood and NTFP value chain.

Themes	Existing	Requests
1. Resource development (human resources)	1.1. Qualified human resources (teachers, researchers, technicians, engineers) 1.2. Existing laboratories (anatomy, chemistry, mechanics and physics) on the Libreville and Franceville sites	1.1.1 Training: 4 technicians, four masters, four theses, four postdocs 1.2.1 Strengthening of 4 laboratories <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wood anatomy • Microtome, episcopy/camera, microscope, heating systems, stains, sander, binocular magnifier: • Durability, mycology • Climatic chamber, UV host, autoclave, ovens, refrigerators; • Chemistry • Infrared, chromatography, UV-Visible • Physics and mechanics • 100 kN universal presses, climatic chamber
2. Resource development (plant resources)	2.1. Raw materials (wood and NTFPs) and little-used or unused species 2.2. Existing laboratories	2.1.1 Density analysis for little-used and unused species to estimate carbon sequestration in wood. 2.2.2 Laboratory reinforcement

5.4.3 Key partners

The key partners to be mobilized for the development of the sustainable wood value chain are:

- The State (Ministry of Water and Forests, Ministry of Higher Education, Ministry of the Economy);
- Socio-economic partners and inter-professional structures;
- CENAREST and its relevant institutes (IRT, IRET, IPHAMETRA, IRAF), ENEF, ENSET, ENS, USTM and ITO.
- Regional partners (RIFFEAC, CEEAC, CEMAC, COMIFAC);
- International partners: LERMAB, ENSTIB/Université de Lorraine, Université Clermont Auvergne, Xylomat/Université de Pau et des Pays de l'Adour, CIRAD, INRAE, ESB/Nantes.

5.4.4 Relationships

The success of the value chain pillar of the timber and non-timber forest products industry depends on the financial contributions of the following players:

- Agence Nationale des Bourses du Gabon (ANBG);
- Socio-economic partners;
- CAFI;

- Embassy technical support services.

5.4.5 Channels

The channels for popularizing and promoting the sustainable timber and NTFP value chain are listed below:

- Media (TV, newspapers);
- Social networks;
- A newsletter published by specialists in wood science and technology in Gabon (LaReVa Bois newsletter);
- Congresses, conferences, etc.

5.4.6 Costs structures

The costs associated with structuring research supporting the sustainable wood and NTFP value chain are presented in the "budget estimates" section. The laboratories and other designations are divided between LaReVa Bois's Libreville and Franceville sites.

5.4.7 Impacts

The sustainable wood and NTFP value chain pillar will have an impact on several sectors:

- Society (combating unemployment and improving quality of life);
- The environment (reducing carbon footprint by reusing co-products that are often burnt);
- The State (increased GDP);
- Socio-economic operators (manufacture of new products and added value to related products);
- The scientific community (access to further knowledge, job creation, opening up of new sectors, technology transfer, etc.).

5.5 Prioritization

<p><i>Short-term:</i> Implemented within the next three years</p>	<p><i>Medium-term:</i> Scheduled for implementation between years three and six</p>	<p><i>Long-term:</i> Planned for implementation beyond the next six years</p>
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Key deliverables

- New academic training courses at USTM (Wood Process Engineering, Bioresource Management and Valorization) and masters internships, start of theses;
- Installation and deployment of a wood science engineer at the Libreville and Franceville sites;
- Equipping the first third with laboratory equipment, training technicians/engineers, setting up pilot units for industrial lines;
- Provision of several prototypes: particleboard, standardized extracts of resins, bark and xylem from wood-related products and Gabonese NTFPs for use in cosmetics and pharmaceuticals and to combat termites and wood rot.
- Sub-regional and international expansion of the USTM's range of training courses, thesis defences, and reception of the first post-docs;
- Equipping the second and third thirds with laboratory equipment, completing technician/engineer training and upgrading pilot units;
- Mass production and marketing of composite materials and other chemical products in growth markets.
- Evaluation, review and monitoring of training/job matching;
- Sustainability and growth of industrial activities, consolidation of transfer activities from universities/research centres to companies;
- Acquire new local consumption habits in favour of new materials and other high value-added products, and gain market share in the sub-region.

5.6 Budget estimates

The following table presents a budget estimate (k€) of the various cost structure elements for the sustainable wood and NTFP value chain.

Designation	Composition	Cost in k€
Operation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wood Science Engineer Attaché (e) with a mission to support academic and professional training for university-enterprise transfer). Duration (3 years). 	131
Equipment/infrastructures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anatomy and microstructure of wood and NTFPs; • Chemistry of extractives and lignocellulosic polymers; • Durability, mycology and microbiology of timber and NTFPs; • Physics and mechanics of wood and lignocellulosic materials. 	200
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vehicles (2) (purchase of a new 4x4 Land cruiser is estimated at 80 MFCFA/Gabon, i.e. around 122 K€x2) 	244
Missions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Installation and configuration of laboratory equipment (4); • Technology transfer and training of technicians in industrial processes (4); • Teaching (4). 	30
Staff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Laboratory technicians (4); • Research Masters (4); • Doctoral theses (4); 	636

	• Postdoc (4)	
TOTAL		1241

5.7 List of participants

	Name	Institution	Fonction	E-mail	Presential/Visio
1	Saint Bickolard Mabicka Iwangou	CENAREST	IRT	saintbickolard@yahoo.fr	P
2	Rodrigue Safou Tchiamia	USTM	Directeur adjoint du Laboratoire de Recherche et de Valorisation du Matériau Bois (LaReVa Bois)	r_safioutchiama@yahoo.fr	P
3	Prudence Yombiyeni	CENAREST	Directrice adjointe de l'IRT	pyombiyeni@gmail.com	P
4	Alain Billand	CIRAD	Dir.	alain.billand@cirad.fr	P

6 One Health: Development of tools for early detection and large-scale zoonotic surveillance, Identification of pathogens in the bushmeat industry, Gorilla health as a sentinel of human impact on the natural environment

6.1 Introduction

The sudden appearance of diseases such as Nipah virus in 1998 (Malaysia), West Nile virus in 1999 (USA), severe acute respiratory syndrome in 2002 (China), highly pathogenic avian influenza in 2003 (Thailand), SARS-CoV-2 in 2019 (China), the frequent recurrence of Ebola epidemics, the maintenance of HAT or malaria (sub-Saharan Africa), could be explained by the existence of wildlife reservoirs for these pathogens (Lau, Susanna K.P. et

al. 2005⁸ ; AbuBakar et al., 2004⁹ ; Njiokou et al., 2006¹⁰ ; Leroy et al., 2004¹¹ ; Jones et al., 2008¹²). The speed at which these diseases have been spreading since the development of rapid transport and the immense cost they generate for the global economy further accentuate the need to understand their ecology, mode, and transmission mechanism to gain complete control over them.

Indeed, over 60% of new human infectious diseases are of zoonotic origin, with nearly 75% coming from wildlife (Jones et al., 2008; Woolhouse et al., 2008¹³).

Gabon, located in the heart of the Congo-Ogooué basin, is 85% forested, 26% of which is legally protected. Today, the country is considered one of the last refuges of tropical animal biodiversity. This fauna is estimated to have around 198 species of mammals, 680 species of birds, 98 species of amphibians, and 95 to 160 reptiles (Lee et al., 2006¹⁴).

Despite its protected status, this biodiversity is an essential resource for local communities and is intended to play a role in the country's economy. In addition to meeting food needs, this natural resource is also important for regulating the forest ecosystem and, therefore, the climate before becoming an asset for ecotourism development. However, all these activities encourage human-wildlife contact, illustrating a real veterinary and public health risk (Boundenga et al., 2023¹⁵).

The challenges associated with this theme are manifold:

- Animal biodiversity plays an important role in the regeneration of forest cover and, thus, in mitigating the impact of climate change, justifying the strong need to preserve it;
- However, the preservation of this fauna entails a sharp increase in population densities and the multiplication of contacts with man, leading respectively to difficulties in coexistence with the latter, resulting in, among other things, Man-Wildlife Conflict and the risk of transmission of zoonotic diseases;
- The success of the policy to protect these emblematic animal species, known as "Umbrella Species", depends on their economic enhancement through the development of ecotourism;

⁸ Lau, Susanna K.P. et al. 2005. "Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus-like Virus in Chinese Horseshoe Bats." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 102(39): 14040–45.

⁹ AbuBakar, S., Chang, L. Y., Ali, A. M., Sharifah, S. H., Yusoff, K., & Zamrod, Z. (2004). Isolation and molecular identification of Nipah virus from pigs. *Emerging infectious diseases*, 10(12), 2228.

¹⁰ Njiokou, F., Laveissière, C., Simo, G., Nkinin, S., Grébaud, P., Cuny, G., & Herder, S. (2006). Wild fauna as a probable animal reservoir for *Trypanosoma brucei gambiense* in Cameroon. *Infection, genetics and evolution*, 6(2), 147-153.

¹¹ Leroy, Eric M et al. 2004. "Multiple Ebola Virus Transmission Events and Rapid Decline of Central African Wildlife." *Science (New York, N.Y.)* 303(5656): 387–90.

¹² Jones et al., 2008

¹³ Woolhouse, M. E., Howey, R., Gaunt, E., Reilly, L., Chase-Topping, M., & Savill, N. (2008). Temporal trends in the discovery of human viruses. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 275(1647), 2111-2115.

¹⁴ Lee, M E et al. 2006. "Le Complexe d'Aires Protégées de Gamba: Une Illustration de La Biodiversité Du Gabon." *Gamba, Gabon: biodiversité d'une forêt équatoriale africaine / Gamba, Gabon: biodiversity of an equatorial African rainforest* (12): 1–15.

¹⁵ Boundenga, L., Makouloutou-Nzassi, P., & Ngoubangoye, B. (2023). A review of Gabonese gorillas and their pathogens: Diversity, transfer and One Health approach to avoid future outbreaks?. *Frontiers in Parasitology*, 2, 1115316.

- All these activities can only thrive if there is constant upstream monitoring of possible outbreaks and reappearances of zoonoses;
- So, alongside empirical methods, it is imperative to define new methods, techniques and tools that are more effective and better adapted to large-scale zoonotic surveillance.

6.2 Aims, activities and expected results

<p>General objectives</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop new, effective and appropriate tools for monitoring large-scale zoonoses; • Identify zoonotic reservoirs in and around national parks; • Understand the modes of transmission of infectious agents such as zoonotic Plasmodium, zoonotic Trypanosoma and some arboviruses known in the region to prevent the emergence or re-emergence of zoonoses in Gabon; • Characterize pathogens in the bushmeat sector consumed in densely populated provinces such as Estuaire through two innovative approaches; • Establish a zoonotic surveillance system that provides key data on the impact of anthropogenic actions on the health status of wildlife; • Train Master's and PhD students and early-career scientists in the new methods, techniques and tools developed.
<p>Key activities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tools for early detection and monitoring of zoonoses: Develop and calibrate the use of hematophagous arthropods (tsetse flies, mosquitoes) for non-invasive early detection and large-scale zoonotic surveillance; • Bushmeat pathogens: Develop sampling and detection strategies for pathogens circulating in the bushmeat industry; • The health of gorillas as sentinels of human impact on their environment: Using fresh samples of faeces and discarded chewed plants, monitor the health status of western lowland gorillas (<i>Gorilla gorilla</i>) by searching for antibiotic resistance genes along a gradient of anthropization from habituated to wild groups.
<p>Expected results</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tools and methodologies for early detection and monitoring of large-scale zoonoses; • Isolation of zoonotic viral, bacterial and parasitic strains from wild animals; • Identification of wildlife zoonoses and associated reservoirs in Gabon; • Mapping of risk zones for pathogens and associated host organisms; • Establishing a correlation between the health status of gorillas and the progressive impact of anthropogenic action in their living environment; • Proposing decision-making tools.

6.3 Detailed activity plan

6.3.1 Social value proposition

<p>Tools for early detection and monitoring of zoonoses</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preventing the risk of infection by zoonotic pathogens; • Population health and well-being; • Production of valuable information for developing ecotourism circuits.
<p>Pathogens in the bushmeat industry</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preventing the risk of infection in the bushmeat industry; • Welfare and public health; • Rational game management; • Production of information to achieve 30x30 objectives.
<p>Gorilla health as a sentinel of human impact on their environment</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Protecting the great apes; • Development of ecotourism; • Job creation; • Involvement of local communities in conservation efforts.

6.3.2 Beneficiaries

- **Gabonese society**, including urban and rural dwellers and indigenous peoples;
- **Knowledge** for managers, stakeholders (NGOs, companies), public authorities;
- **Better cooperation** between the academic and technical community;
- **Regional benefit:** economic enhancement of biodiversity through the development of ecotourism;
- **Global benefit for the planet:** preservation of biodiversity and climate regulation.

6.3.3 Key activities

Tools for early detection and monitoring of zoonoses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Calibration of the method for using tsetse flies as a non-invasive means of detecting infectious agents in wildlife; • Developing tsetse traps suitable for monitoring large-scale zoonoses (traps capable of keeping tsetse alive for 7 to 10 days).
Pathogens in the bushmeat industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish a chain of custody for bushmeat among hunters, traders and even conservation officers, who very often find dead animal carcasses in the forest; • Search for pathogens circulating in bushmeat.
Gorilla health as a sentinel of human impact on their environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sample fresh gorilla faeces, then collect plants chewed and discarded by gorillas; • Search for zoonotic and anthroozoonotic pathogens characterised by antibiotic resistance genes and reflect human impact on natural environments.

6.3.4 Key resources

Theme 1: Tools for early detection and monitoring of zoonoses		
Activities	Existing	Requests
1.1. Develop a tsetse fly trap and a mosquito trap capable of capturing and keeping hematophagous flies alive for 7 to 10 days.	<p>1.1.1 Modelled on existing tsetse fly and mosquito traps. For example, in the VAVOUA trap, the shape and the black and Phtalogen blue colours remain the same</p> <p>1.1.2. A Partner team in France has already adapted An adaptation model of the Cone above the trap, and many other VAVOUA trap accessories have also been adjusted.</p>	<p>1.1.1 Production in France, in reasonable quantities (300 to 500) of the new trap adapted from the VAVOUA trap</p> <p>1.1.2 Reinforcement of VAVOUA traps to have the same quantity as the new trap</p> <p>1.1.3 Acquisition and reinforcement of equipment for the conservation and treatment of captured hematophagous flies</p> <p>1.1.4 Mobility and field facilities.</p>
1.2. Compare the effectiveness of the two (02) trap types (old and new) in capturing tsetse flies and mosquitoes, then compare the rates of	1.2.1. Research super-sites that are rich in biodiversity. This is the case of sites located in the Ivindo (Ipassa station), Moukalaba-doudou (Doussala station) and Lopé (Lopé station) national parks	<p>1.2.1 Availability of all traps in Libreville</p> <p>1.2.2 Availability in Libreville of equipment for preserving and processing captured blood-sucking insects</p> <p>1.2.3 Mobility and field facilities.</p>

swallowed flies collected in every kind of trap.	1.2.2. Good expertise and reasonably good knowledge of the study mentioned above areas.	
1.3. Install permanent zoonosis monitoring systems around the super-sites.	1.3.1. Supersites for research, rich in biodiversity. This is the case for sites located in the Ivindo (Ipassa station), Moukalaba-doudou (Doussala station) and Lopé (Lopé station) national parks 1.3.2. Available expertise and methodologies.	1.3.1 Molecular analysis laboratory, with P3 security level 1.3.2 Genomics platform accessible to all partners (environment, animal health, human health) 1.3.3 Mobility and field facilities.

Theme 2: Pathogens in the bushmeat industry

Activities	Existing	Requests
2.1. Establish a chain for safely collecting bushmeat samples from hunters, traders and conservation officers.	2.1.1 List existing bushmeat markets in the country's major towns and identify their supply chain 2.1.2 Establish a contract with conversation agents and train them to systematically remove pieces of meat from animal corpses found in the forest.	2.1.1. Capacity building for researchers and field technicians 2.1.2. Equipment and tools for the bushmeat processing and analysis chain 2.1.3 Mobility and field facilities.
2.2. Search for infectious agents in bushmeat.	2.2.1 Bushmeat collected from hunters, traders and others 2.2.2 Human resources	2.2.1. Molecular analysis laboratory, with P3 security level 2.2.2. Standardized genomics platform for environmental, animal and human health issues 2.2.3. Mobility and field amenities.

Theme 3: Gorilla health as a sentinel of human impact on their environment

Activities	Existing	Requests
3.1. Collect and analyze fresh faecal samples from gorillas in the forest.	3.1.1 Ipassa and Doussala super-sites 3.1.2 High gorilla density in Moukalaba-Doudou National Park 3.1.3 Existence of habituated and semi-habituated gorilla groups.	3.1. Capacity building for researchers and field technicians 3.2. Equipment and tools for the faecal matter processing and analysis chain 3.3. Standardized genomics platform for environmental, animal and human health issues 3.4. Mobility and field amenities.
3.2. Forest sampling and analysis of plants chewed and rejected by gorillas.	3.2.1 Ipassa and Doussala super-sites 3.2.2 High gorilla density in Moukalaba-Doudou National Park	3.1. Capacity building for researchers and field technicians

	3.2.3 Existence of habituated and semi-habituated gorilla groups.	<p>3.2. Equipment and tools for the plant material processing and analysis chain</p> <p>3.3. Standardized genomics platform for environmental, animal and human health issues</p> <p>3.4. Mobility and on-site amenities.</p>
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6.3.5 Key partners

Gabon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IRET-CENAREST, CIRMF, ANPN, USTM, CERMEL, Ministries of Scientific Research, Health, Agriculture, Environment
France	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MIVEGEC-IRD-Montpellier, CNRS, CIRAD, Université de Bourgogne et de Franche Comté

6.3.6 Relationships

Networks between national academic institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gabon's research partners are connected on One Health issues CERMEL-CENAREST; IRET-CERMEL; ENEF-IRET; USTM-ENEF; USS-CIRMF; UOB-CENAREST; ANPN-CENAREST
Networks between sub-regional academic institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> University of Yaoundé-CENAREST; CERMEL-FCRM (Fondation Congolaise pour la Recherche Médicale); University of Yaoundé-CERMEL; IP Bangui-CIRMF;
Networks between international academic institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> University of Nagasaki-IRET-CERMEL; CENAREST-IRD; IRD-CIRMF; Université de Bourgogne –IRET; University of Bourgogne-USTM; CIRAD-CENAREST; University of Kyoto-CENAREST; GRAVIR; CAIDERA: Central African Infectious Disease and Epidemics Research Alliance, USTM-IRDUSTM-ANPN-CRID (Cameroun)
Relations with stakeholders (political decision-makers): To be developed with the creation of a national One Health platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ministries in charge of public health, higher education and scientific research, environment and forestry, livestock farming ONGS WCS, WWF, BRAINFOREST...

6.3.7 Channels

Search for funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consortiums, UMR, Calls for projects, Lobbying...
Data collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Obtain the necessary research authorizations Establish partnership agreements with local, national and international institutions and players, Field sampling, bushmeat seizures (Eaux et forêts, ANPN), health structures, field stations, volunteer patients, livestock farms, AGEOS...
Data analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National, regional, and international technical platforms, databases, AGEOS, etc.
Communication and digital action plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interdisciplinary exchanges to promote knowledge transfer (workshops) and international and sub-regional mobility, Scientific valorization (publications, scientific communications, symposia), Public awareness and outreach (media and other audiences) Communication for decision-makers (summary reports and recommendations)

6.3.8 Structures and costs

The One Health activity falls more within the scope of the PREZODE initiative but has strong links with the Country Package Gabon's plant and animal biodiversity issues. However, the general cost structure of the "One Health" theme could be as follows:

Staff	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Salaries and benefits for principal investigators, collaborators and support staff. Training and professional development costs (capacity building for researchers, students, engineers and technicians, postdocs, etc.). Recruitment of PhDs, postdocs, IT and project managers.
Equipment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Costs of purchasing or leasing specialized equipment required for research.
Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Costs of renovating existing laboratories and research stations (e.g. supersites) and building new ones.
Consumables	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Laboratory materials, office supplies, chemicals, etc.
Travel and accommodation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Travel to conferences, meet collaborators, or conduct field or laboratory work.
Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communication costs, including access to databases, specialized journals, software subscriptions, etc.
Administrative expenses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project administration overhead includes management costs, legal services, accounting services, etc.
Subcontracting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Costs associated with the purchase of specialized services.
Dissemination of results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Costs associated with publishing research results, organizing conferences, etc.
Evaluation and follow-up	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expenses related to evaluating the project and monitoring its progress.

6.3.9 Impacts

Impact 1:	Better understanding of zoonotic risk	Improved knowledge of disease transmission risks optimized use of animal resources consumed as bushmeat.
Impact 2:	Improved surveillance, prevention or mitigation	Crucial technical support for public health, conservation and ecotourism development.
Impact 3:	Establishment of reference laboratories	Improving existing technical platforms and setting up other technological platforms needed to conduct all analyses on-site in Libreville.
Impact 4:	Increased attractiveness to international donors and collaborators	The practice of quality research in the targeted fields will create a climate of trust between research teams and funding agencies.
Impact 5:	Increased critical mass of better-trained personnel	Improve the quality of the country's human resources in the targeted fields.

6.3.10 Prioritization

The following table presents a three-year plan for the implementation of deliverables.

Keys deliverables	Short-term: Implemented within the next three years	Medium-term: Scheduled for implementation between years three and six	Long-term: Planned for implementation beyond the next six years
Tools for early detection and monitoring of zoonoses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operation: Strengthening field research capabilities (vehicles, encoding tools, capacity building) • Infrastructures: Upgrading of the existing molecular analysis laboratory at IRET-CENAREST. • Equipment: Acquisition of laboratory equipment (freezers, refrigerators, thermocyclers, etc.) and field equipment (tsetse traps, sample collection and conservation equipment). • Training: PhD (n=2), master's scholarships (n=4), field workers • Data strategy: Server, supercomputer 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infrastructures: Construction of a molecular analysis laboratory to international standards, with P3 security • Equipment: Reinforcement of laboratory and field equipment • Personnel: Positions for Genomics Engineers, Bioinformaticians, Modellers • Personnel: Capacity building in biostatistics, sampling techniques and data analysis • Training: PhD (n=4), master's scholarships (n=6), field actors (including MOOC) • Data strategy: Data management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operation: Support for permanent zoonotic surveillance in super-sites • Training: Master's scholarships (n=6), field actors (including MOOC) • Workshops: Support for curriculum revision • Data strategy: Data management
Bushmeat pathogens	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operation: Strengthening field research capabilities (vehicles, encoding tools) • Equipment: Field (sampling and conservation) and laboratory equipment • Personnel: Capacity building for researchers and technicians • Infrastructures: Upgrading the existing laboratory at IRET • Training: PhD (n=2), master's scholarships (n=4), field actors (including MOOC) • Data strategy: Data management plan, data management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Infrastructures: Construction of a molecular analysis laboratory to international standards, with P3 security • Equipment: Reinforcement of laboratory and field equipment • Training: PhD (n=2), master's scholarships (n=4), field actors (including MOOC) • Data strategy: Data management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operation: Strengthening field research capabilities (vehicles, encoding tools) • Equipment: Reinforcement of equipment and field equipment • Training: Master's scholarships (n=3), field actors (including MOOC) • Data strategy: Data management

Gorilla health as a sentinel of human impact on their environment

- **Operation:** Strengthening field research capabilities (vehicles, encoding tools)
 - **Equipment:** Field (sampling and conservation) and laboratory equipment
 - **Personnel:** Capacity building for researchers and technicians
 - **Infrastructure:** Upgrading of existing CIRMF and USTM laboratories
 - **Training:** PhD (n=2), master's scholarships (n=4), field actors (including MOOC)
 - **Data strategy:** Data management plan, data management
- **Infrastructure:** Reinforcement of existing molecular analysis laboratories at CIRMF and USTM, with P3 security
 - **Equipment:** Reinforcement of laboratory and field equipment
 - **Training:** PhD (n=2), master's scholarships (n=4), field actors (including MOOC)
 - **Data strategy:** Data management
- **Operation:** Strengthening field research capabilities (vehicles, encoding tools)
 - **Equipment:** Reinforcement of laboratory and field equipment
 - **Training:** Master's scholarships (n=3), field actors (including MOOC)
 - **Data strategy:** Data management

6.4 Budget estimates

The budget estimate is broken down as follows.

	Equipment	Operation	Personnel	Total (€)
1. Tools for early detection and monitoring of zoonoses	550 000	180 000	256 000	986 000
○ 1.1. Development, calibration and production of the new type of Tsetse Trap	200 000	70 000	0	270 000
○ 1.2. Large-scale zoonotic surveillance	350 000	50 000		400 000
○ 1.3. Training		40 000	256 000	296 000
○ 1.4. Data strategy		20 000	0	20 000
2. Bushmeat pathogens	200 000	126 000	210 000	536 000
○ 2.1. Collecting bushmeat and testing for circulating infectious agents	200 000	96 000	0	296 000
○ 2.2. Training		10 000	210 000	220 000
○ 2.3. Data strategy		20 000	0	20 000
3. Gorilla health as a sentinel of human impact on their environment	480 000	480 000	256 000	1 216 000
○ 3.1. Sampling of faeces and chewed plants in supersites	240 000	100 000	0	340 000
○ 3.2. Sample processing and molecular analysis	240 000	200 000		440 000
○ 3.3. Training		40 000	256 000	296 000
○ 3.4. Data strategy		140 000	0	140 000
4. Management and communication			200 000	200 000
○ 4.1. VI			100 000	100 000
○ 4.2. Expatriates			100 000	100 000
Total	1 230 000	786 000	922 000	2 938 000

6.5 List of participants

	Name	Institution	Fonction	E-mail	Presential/Visio
1	Paul Yannick Bitome Essono	CENAREST	IRET	bitomessono@yahoo.fr	P
2	Judicael Obame Nkoghe	USTM	CIRMF	judicael.obame@live.fr	V
3	Chimène Nze Nkoghe	CENAREST	IRET	nzechimene@gmail.com	P
4	Boris Makanga	CENAREST	IRET	makanga.boris@gmail.com	P
5	Dieudonné Nkoghe	Min. Santé		dnkoghe@hotmail.com	P
6	Émelie Arlette Apinda	CENAREST	IRET	ea.apindalegnouo@yahoo.fr	P
7	Larson Boudenga	CIRMF		boundenga@gmail.com	V
8	Christophe Zinga	CIRMF		zinga.koumba39@yahoo.com	P
9	Yvon Bert Pambou	CENAREST	IRET	yvonbertpambou@gmail.com	P
10	Christophe Paupy	IRD	MIVEGEC	christophe.paupy@ird.fr	V

7 Coastal and marine environments

F. Le Loc'h and J. H. Mve Beh gave an oral presentation on the first day. The working groups did not deal with it during these days. This aspect of the CP-Gabon will be the subject of a specific workshop in the coming months concerning the implementation of the Blue Bond, recently signed by the Gabonese government.

Gabon boasts a mosaic of exceptional marine and coastal ecosystems, still primarily preserved but subject to multiple pressures such as overfishing, plastic and chemical pollution, urbanization and coastal erosion, which affect fragile coastal ecosystems such as mangroves. Between this natural heritage and the combined threats of human activities and climate change, there is a pressing need for spatial planning to ensure the spatio-temporal cohabitation of all activities. Indeed, the effective and efficient management of maritime spaces is at the heart of strategic planning by states and non-state entities interested in preserving aquatic biodiversity, the deep seabed and other aquatic spaces. Control of these areas, rich in aquatic resources, is a major global challenge for States and remains a priority for developing an inclusive and sustainable blue economy that significantly contributes to the transformation and growth of Gabon as part of an integrated development framework.

Gabon's coastal and marine areas contribute to the world's significant ecological balance. Today, the coastal region is a symbol of African nature that is still largely unspoiled and has a dual originality thanks to its maritime and climatic influences: the diversity and richness of Gabon's coastal fauna are determined by the major marine ecosystems and the

Congo Basin. Gabon's marine waters are unique in that most of them belong to the ecosystem known as the southern alternation zone of the Gulf of Guinea, which stretches from Cape Lopez (in Gabon) to Cape Frio (in Angola). Cape Lopez thus marks the boundary of the transition zone between the warm, desalinated waters of the Gulf of Guinea (with relatively low productivity) to the north and the cold, salty waters of the Benguela Current (with high productivity) to the south.

These environments, which comprise Gabon's coastal and marine territory, are original from a natural point of view and constitute a genuine natural capital of high ecological value that must be preserved and managed sustainably.

Marine and coastal areas have become Gabon's most "coveted" territories. They are now home to most of the country's centres of gravity: highly uneven human occupation and hyper-concentration of human activities, including fishing, oil, forestry and mining. Awareness of the coastline is crucial: it embodies a space for the future, where consultation and coordination of strategies, plans and actions, and more generally of coastal policies, are essential due to its multiple uses in an environment where ecosystems are rich but fragile, requiring a sustainable approach to integrated management. Gabon's marine and coastal environments are directly confronted with the issue of global change: indiscriminate fishing, rising sea levels, coastal erosion, pollution, flooding, and risks linked to the development problems inherent to cities in fast-growing developing countries.

The main objectives related to this theme are:

- Marine biodiversity conservation (marine protected areas and aquatic reserves),
- Fisheries monitoring and control (at sea and on land),
- Coastal urbanization, Industrialization of the Ogooué watershed,
- The land/sea continuum (contamination, critical habitats, etc.),
- Nutritional quality/health risk monitoring (water, fish, etc.),
- Blue carbon.

8 Workshop summary

The Gabon-France workshop on setting up the scientific and capacity-building component of the CP-Gabon was held over three days to define research needs, intervention targets and financial components. This first workshop brought together 39 Gabonese and 29 French scientists. The event was a significant opportunity for those in the room and by videoconference to collaborate closely, building solid partnerships and establishing a concrete action plan to strengthen the region's scientific research and conservation capacity. It helped ensure a better understanding of the scientific programming issues involved in supporting the protection of Gabon's socio-ecosystems through an integrated vision considering the ambitious objectives of combating climate change and preserving biodiversity. The technical part of the workshop was carried out with the collaboration of Société d'Incubation Numérique du Gabon (SING SA, <https://www.sing.ga/>) in their premises equipped with spacious rooms and a videoconferencing system. SING helped organize the workshop by proposing its method

for producing OKRs (*Objectives Key Results*). This method proved particularly well-suited to the needs of scientific framing in a multi-institutional and international context.

The workshop focused mainly on the five pillars of the One Forest Vision (OFV) initiative proposed at the One Forest Summit in March 2023. This initiative, financially supported by the French Ministries of Higher Education and Research (MESR) and Europe and Foreign Affairs (MEAE), aims to provide scientific evidence for conserving the environmental integrity of biodiversity and irretrievable carbon reservoirs in tropical forests. OFV plans to provide transparent, user-friendly, near-real-time monitoring of forest degradation, carbon stocks and biodiversity in the Congo Basin, particularly those coordinated by France. The workshop was financially supported by OFV and a Fonds de solidarité pour les projets innovants (FSPI-R) from the French Embassy in Gabon.

The morning of November 22 was devoted to a high-level protocol opening in the conference room of the Ministry of Water and Forests, under the aegis of Colonel Maurice NTOSSUI ALLOGHO, Minister of Water and Forests, Environmental Preservation, in charge of Climate and Human-Wildlife Conflict, Professor Hervé NDOUME ESSINGONE, Minister of Higher Education, Scientific Research and Technological Innovation, and His Excellency the French Ambassador to Gabon, Alexis LAMEK. Before the opening addresses by the French Ambassador and the Minister of Water and Forests, the protocol sequence began with a presentation of the challenges and expectations of the event. Pr Alfred NGOMANDA presented the Gabonese side, while Dr Laurent DURIEUX introduced the French side. Protocol did not allow the Minister of Higher Education and Scientific Research to speak. In addition to the workshop participants themselves, many key personalities attended the opening, including Directors General and Secretaries General of Ministries, Cabinet Members of Ministers, the Director of AFD-Gabon, the Cooperation and Cultural Action Counsellor and the Scientific Attaché of the French Embassy. The opening ceremony ended with a family photo and a cocktail reception for the guests. As for the workshop participants, they moved on to the SING SA premises for further work.

The afternoon of November 22 began with the participants settling in and an introductory word from SING SA explaining their methodology for defining OKRs. Speakers made technical presentations from both sides. The topics covered included (1) coastal and marine environments, (2) One Health, (3) animal biodiversity conservation, umbrella species, wildlife-environment interactions and human-wildlife conflict management, and (4) reliable carbon balance, plant biodiversity conservation and land use. Participants were divided into three working groups for the thematic axes (2), (3), and (4), the last two being those directly linked to OFV.

The day of November 23 was entirely devoted to the work of the thematic groups. A new thematic group on promoting sustainable value chains in the forest industry emerged from the "reliable carbon balance" group.

The morning of November 24 was devoted to a plenary presentation of the work carried out by the working groups.

The afternoon of November 24 was devoted to drawing up/validating the roadmap, and the days ended with closing speeches by personalities such as Dr. Jean-François SOUSSANA (VP INRAE), Dr. Alain BILLAND (Director Impact CIRAD), Prof. Stephan NTIE (CS ANPN), Dr. Donald MIDOKO IPONGA (CENAREST/IRET), and Prof. Alfred NGOMANDA (CG CENAREST).

The most salient results are:

- Stakeholders' understanding of the CP-Gabon and the synergy initiated between the OFV and CBSI initiatives,
- OFV's main lines of action are validated for Gabon for the next four years,
- Avenues of collaboration are identified for OFV-related actions: marine and coastal environments, the One Health initiative and the promotion of sustainable value chains in the forest industry,
- Needs in terms of human resources, infrastructure and equipment are identified for the implementation of CP-Gabon's scientific actions,
- The OFV roadmap and implementation agreement to support the CP-Gabon are validated and signed.

Quantifying the needs expressed in 2024 is still necessary, considering various actions such as staff reinforcement, skills development, equipment acquisition, infrastructure development, and mission execution. The budget allocation also needs to be studied in greater depth, given that the amounts remain unknown at this stage except for the OFV contribution, and their distribution between the various players involved needs to be defined. This will require further discussions and a new workshop.

8.1 Group 1: Reliable carbon balance, conservation of plant biodiversity and land use

This first thematic group comprised 11 and 5 Gabonese and French scientists from 7 and 4 research and higher education institutions. Research needs and priority actions concerning plant biodiversity conservation, carbon balance, and land use were addressed sequentially, and strong links between these three components and with the other thematic groups were identified, notably around supersites. Discussions also led to a fourth thematic group focusing on timber and non-timber forest product value chains, which developed its analysis framework. About plant biodiversity, the essential role played by the Gabonese National Herbarium was underlined, as was the role played by CENAREST's Institut de Recherche en Écologie Tropicale (IRET) and the Agence Nationale des Parcs Nationaux (ANPN) via the Inventaire des Ressources Naturelles (IRN) for carbon assessment, and by the Agence Gabonaise d'Études et Observations Spatiales (AGEOS) for land-use mapping. While the skills and infrastructure are undeniable, significant support is needed to develop ambitious biodiversity and carbon conservation strategies, anchor research projects with a high scientific impact, and train future generations in these new challenges. In particular, this involves rehabilitating existing infrastructures (national herbarium, laboratories, research stations) while ensuring the essential operation of laboratories and stations (vehicles, generators, fuel, internet access), which can then be better mobilized for the field training of teams (botany) and students (botany, dendrometry). The sheer volume of knowledge generated will require an equally ambitious data strategy, from collection to analysis, including quality control, archiving and availability. The beneficiaries are diverse, from Gabonese society to global decision-makers, with impacts such as value chain optimization, preservation of cultural value, contribution to the fight against climate change, and sustainable ecosystem management.

8.2 Group 2: Conservation of animal biodiversity, umbrella species, wildlife-environment interaction, management of human-wildlife conflict

The thematic group comprised 14 Gabonese and 3 French scientists. Faced with rapid changes in global biodiversity, knowledge and governance issues are crucial to preserving the Congo Basin forests. The group formulated six significant objectives: biodiversity assessment, its contribution to ecosystems, human-wildlife coexistence, local community involvement, capacity building and data management. Key activities include assessments, interaction studies, measures for peaceful coexistence, valorization of local knowledge, capacity building, and the establishment of data infrastructures. Expected results include a better understanding of biodiversity, community benefits, increased scientific visibility, harmonious coexistence, and quality data for decision-making. The detailed activity plan, key partners, cost structure and impacts are also defined, with prioritization over the short, medium and long-term.

8.3 Group 3: Promoting sustainable value chains in the forest industry

The theme presented is the Gabonese government's initiative to process logs locally, increasing wood industry waste. This under-exploited biomass, associated with non-timber forest products (NTFPs), is targeted by the "Wood and NTFP value chain" pillar. This pillar aims to fill knowledge gaps through research and development in partnership with Gabonese and French institutions. The aim is to harness these untapped resources to create high value-added products, such as composite materials, bio-sourced molecules and nutritious foods. The success of this initiative depends on scientific support, an interdisciplinary approach and national capacity building. Expected impacts include industrial development, job creation, improvement of the quality of research, and strengthening of cooperation between Gabon and France. Priority beneficiaries include the labour market, socio-economic operators, the State, the national scientific community, and development NGOs. Key activities involve training, capacity building, and producing composite materials and high value-added molecules. The social value proposition is based on creating diversified jobs, optimising by-products, and training. The wide-ranging impacts will affect society, the environment, the State, socio-economic operators and the scientific community. The detailed business plan covers teaching, research and complementary activities. Key resources required are summarized, and key partners include government entities, academic institutions, and international partners. Success depends on financial contributions. Outreach channels include the media, social networks, specialized newsletters, and academic events. Costs associated with structuring the research are detailed, and expected impacts span the social, environmental, economic and scientific spheres.

8.4 Group 4: One Health: Development of tools for early detection and large-scale zoonotic surveillance, Identification of pathogens in the bushmeat industry, Gorilla health as a sentinel of human impact on the natural environment

The group comprised 9 Gabonese scientists and 1 French scientist. This theme addresses the emerging risks of zoonotic diseases, highlighting the importance of understanding their ecology and transmission, especially in regions like Gabon, rich in biodiversity. Issues at stake include wildlife preservation, human-wildlife coexistence, the protection of emblematic species, and the need for ongoing zoonosis surveillance. Objectives include developing zoonosis monitoring tools, identifying zoonotic reservoirs, understanding modes of transmission, characterizing bushmeat pathogens, and establishing a zoonotic surveillance system. Key activities involve developing early detection tools, searching for pathogens in bushmeat, and using gorillas as sentinels. Expected results include detection tools, identifying pathogens, mapping at-risk areas, and proposals for decision-support tools. The social value proposition of each activity highlights the prevention of infection risks, public health, sustainable management of animal resources, gorilla protection, ecotourism development, and job creation. Beneficiaries include Gabonese society, managers, international partners and the planet. Local and international partners include research institutions, ministries, universities, and non-governmental organizations, forming a solid network to address One Health issues. Channels include obtaining research authorizations, creating partnership agreements, and a multi-level communication plan for public awareness, scientific valorization, and communication with decision-makers. Overall, cost structuring is linked to the PREZODE initiative, with close links to the CP Gabon. Impacts include a better understanding of zoonotic risk, improved surveillance and prevention, the establishment of reference laboratories, increased attractiveness to donors, and a critical mass of better-trained personnel. A three-year plan is proposed, covering capacity building, equipment acquisition, infrastructure upgrades, data collection and analysis, and staff training.

The thematic group was thus able to detail a comprehensive and strategic approach to tackling the challenges of zoonoses in Gabon, emphasising interdisciplinary collaboration, effective surveillance, and raising awareness among various audiences.

9 Conclusions

In his closing speech, Jean-François SOUSSANA emphasised that the workshop had been a remarkable experience, effectively integrating the perspectives of beneficiaries and communities as well as the core values of the research. The participatory approach strengthened commitment and enlightened understanding of local issues. Considering cross-cutting issues in capacity building, education, infrastructure development, and data management gave the project a holistic dimension rooted in local reality.

The thematic analyses have been exceptional, demonstrating an enriching interdisciplinarity. The level of consensus reached underlines the effectiveness of our collaboration. The scientific pillar of the CP-Gabon is clearly defined, underlining the

importance of regional networks and cooperation with other initiatives such as the Congo Basin Science Initiative.

Despite this progress, much remains to be done. Organising an annual workshop is a good way of maintaining the momentum and replicating the experience in the other countries where France is coordinating the CP (Congo, DRC). The imminent launch of the OFV project, focusing on capacity building, training, infrastructure, equipment and data, represents a crucial step towards creating a knowledge-sharing platform.

However, the OFV project will not cover all the components of the CP, with the One Health and wood value chain components requiring additional funding. The reference to the PREZODE initiative on preventing emerging zoonotic diseases is a reminder of the need for collaboration and external financing.

In conclusion, this workshop has laid a solid foundation for fruitful collaboration and a clear roadmap. Implementing the plans and exploring partnership opportunities with other projects and initiatives are now essential to ensure the overall success of the CP in Gabon.

10 APPENDICES

10.1 Workshop support provider

Société d'Incubation Numérique du Gabon (SING SA), Libreville

Centre-Ville, BP 2280, Rue Pecqueur, Libreville

+241 (0) 74 13 71 03

10.2 List of participants in Gabon

	Name	Institution	Fonction	E-mail	Presence/Visio
1	Alfred Ngomanda	CENAREST	Commissaire Général	ngomanda@yahoo.fr	P
2	Aboubakar Mambimba Ndjoungui	AGEOS	Directeur adjoint	abmambimba@gmail.com	P
3	Stephan Ntié	ANPN	Conseiller scientifique	stephanntie@yahoo.fr	P
4	Vincent Midjibé	ANPN		medjibe@gmail.com	P
5	Christopher Orbell	PANTHERA		corbell@panthera.org	P
6	Patrick Mickala	USTM	Vice Recteur	pmickala@gmail.com	P
7	Steeve Ngama	CENAREST	IRAF	ngama.steeve@gmail.com	P
8	Archange Boupoya	CENAREST	IPHAMETRA	boupoyaclay@hotmail.com	P
9	Etienne François Akomo Okoué	CENAREST	IRET	akomookoue1977@gmail.com	P
10	Paul Yannick Bitome Essono	CENAREST	IRET	bitomessono@yahoo.fr	P
11	Philipp Henschel	PANTHERA		phenschel@panthera.org	P
12	Donald Midoko Iponga	CENAREST	IRET	dmiponga@gmail.com	P
13	Judicael Obame Nkoghe	USTM	CIRMF	judicael.obame@live.fr	V
14	Stéphanie Bourgeois	ANPN		stephbourgeois_@hotmail.com	P

15	David Lehmann	OKALA	ARISE	david.lehmann@okala.io	P
16	Jimmy Franck Nzomba	CENAREST	IRET	nzombajimmyfranck@gmail.com	P
17	Blaise Rollinat Mboye	CENAREST	IRAF	mblaiserollinat@gmail.com	P
18	Gaspard Abitsi	WCS		gabitsi@wcs.org	P
19	Franck Rodrigue Oloou Ambounda	CENAREST	IRET	rodfranck@hotmail.com	P
20	Quentin Moundoung Mavouroulou	CENAREST	IRET	moundounga@yahoo.fr	P
21	Raymonde Mboma	CENAREST	IRET	belleorchidey@yahoo.fr	P
22	Rodrigue Safou Tchiana	USTM	Pr.	rodriguesafoutchiana@gmail.com	P
23	Conan Vassily Obame	AGEOS	AGEOS	obameconanvassily@gmail.com	P
24	St Bickolard Mabicka Iwangou	CENAREST	IRT	saintbickolard@yahoo.fr	P
25	Prudence Yombiyeni	CENAREST	IRT	prudence_yom@yahoo.fr	P
26	Jean-Pierre Obame	CENAREST	IRET	jpobame@outlook.com	P
27	Chimène Nze Nkoghe	CENAREST	IRET	nzechimene@gmail.com	P
28	Boris Makanga	CENAREST	IRET	makanga.boris@gmail.com	P
29	Dieudonné Nkoghe	Min. Santé		dnkoghe@hotmail.com	P
30	Emelie Arlette Apinda	CENAREST	IRET		P
31	Larson Boudenga	CIRMF		boundenga@gmail.com	V
32	Raissa Mouketa	Tropicalthèque		raissamouketa@gmail.com	P
33	Christophe Zinga	CIRMF		zinga.koumba39@yahoo.com	P
34	Guy Serge Bignoumba	UOB		gsbignoumba@yahoo.fr	P

35	Yvon Bert Pambou	CENAREST	IRET	yvonbertpambou@gmail.com	P
36	Pulcherie Bissiengou	CENAREST	IFRAMETRA	bissiengou_p@yahoo.fr	P
37	Ephrem Nzengue	CENAREST	IRET	nzengue_ephrem@yahoo.fr	P
38	Guy Max Moussavou	CENAREST	IRSH	mouss.gmx2@gmail.com	P
39	Jean Felicien Liwouwou	CENAREST	IRAF/DGEA	jean_feli@yahoo.fr	P
40	Tierry Diop Bineni	CENAREST	IRET	diopbinenithierry01@gmail.com	P
41	Jean Hervé Mvé Beh	MINEF	DGEA	mormyre69@gmail.com	P

10.3 List of participants in France

	Name	Institution	Fonction	E-mail	Presence/Visio
1	Jean-Francois Soussana	INRAE	Dir.	jean-francois.soussana@inrae.fr	V
2	Alain Billand	CIRAD	Dir.	alain.billand@cirad.fr	P
3	Laurent Durieux	IRD	IR Data Terra	laurent.durieux@ird.fr	P
5	Jérôme Chave	CNRS	UMR EDB	jerome.chave@univ-tlse3.fr	P
7	Sabrina Krief	MNHN	MNHN	sabrina.krief@mnhn.fr	V
8	Philippe Ciais	CEA	LSCE CEA CNRS UVSQ	philippe.ciais@lsce.ipsl.fr	exc
9	Frédéric Frappart	INRAE	INRAE ISPA	frederic.frappart@inrae.fr	V
10	Pierre Couteron	IRD	UMR AMAP	pierre.couteron@ird.fr	exc
12	Nicolas Barbier	IRD	UMR AMAP	nicolas.barbier@ird.fr	P
13	Pierre Ploton	IRD	UMR AMAP	pierre.ploton@ird.fr	V
14	Gilles Dauby	IRD	UMR AMAP	gilles.dauby@ird.fr	exc
15	Vivien Rossi	CIRAD	UR Forêts et Société	vivien.rossi@cirad.fr	exc
16	Hadrien Vantomme	CIRAD	UR Forêts et Société	hadrien.vanthomme@cirad.fr	V
17	Daniel Cornelis	CIRAD	UR Forêts et Société	daniel.cornelis@cirad.fr	exc
18	Adeline Fayolle	CIRAD	UR Forêts et Société	adeline.fayolle@ulg.ac.be	P
19	Daniel Barthélémy	CIRAD	AMAP	daniel.barthelemy@cirad.fr	V
20	Marie Sigaud	MNHN		marie.sigaud@mnhn.fr	P

22	Martin Schwartz	CEA	LSCE	martin.schwartz@lsce.ipsl.fr	P
24	Aurelien de Truchis	KAYROS		a.detruchis@kayros.com	P
26	Christophe Paupy	IRD	MIVEGEC	christophe.paupy@ird.fr	V
27	François Brétagnolle	U. Bourgogne		francois.bretagnolle@u-bourgogne.fr	P
28	François Le Loc'h	IRD	LEMAR	francois.le.loch@ird.fr	P
29	Jean-Jacques Braun	IRD	GET	jean-jacques.braun@ird.fr	P